

Non-Aviation Business: How Airports Transform Passengers into Consumers

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Foreword

In recent decades, airports worldwide have undergone a profound transformation, expanding not only their transportation-related areas due to the increase in passengers but also, and above all, their services and commercial spaces to offer a wide range of shopping opportunities.

Modern airports, therefore, originally established as departure and arrival points for travelers, have evolved into significant shopping destinations. One of the main reasons for this transformation is that many people spend a considerable amount of time in these locations, either waiting for their flight or in transit. Naturally, this has led airport operators to create commercial spaces offering an extensive selection of retail stores, luxury boutiques, international fashion brands, jewelry stores, perfumeries, bookstores, electronics shops, as well as cafes, restaurants, bookshops, duty-free outlets, and a variety of location-specific services.

Analyzing industry data, the trend of flying passengers has exponentially increased due to a series of strategic factors linked to the entry of low-cost airlines into the market and the subsequent reduction in ticket costs, the spread of mass tourism, and the global growth of the middle class. It is noteworthy that this unstoppable trend in air traffic, from the beginning of the new millennium until the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, reached its peak with a staggering 4.6 billion passengers in 2019.

It is clear, therefore, that this flow of passengers passing through airports becomes a very interesting target market for companies engaged in non-aviation business. Non-aeronautical sources of income not only provide a diversification of airports' revenue streams but also serve as an additional cushion during economic recessions. However, the scale of the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting travel restrictions have made the COVID-19 crisis a unique one.

The airport is indeed the first and last point of contact with the passenger before reaching the destination. Here, managers are required to maximize the pleasurable experience within the commercial area. It should be emphasized that all non-aviation revenue strategies start from the concept that shopping is the oldest and most crucial aspect of tourism¹. From this point, and with the addition of technology and information technology expediting the check-in and baggage control process, travelers now have much more free time to spend at the airport. This time is

¹ Vincenzo Fasone, Lukas Kofler, Raffaele Scuderi, *Business performance of airports: non aviation revenues and their determinants*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Vol. 53, June 2016

not confined only to duty-free spaces but extends to a comprehensive "360-degree experience" encompassing food, shopping, reading, music, work, entertainment, and relaxation.

The primary goal of airports' non-aviation business is to offer passengers a complete range of services and shopping options to meet their needs during travel. Simultaneously, this diversification of income allows airports to reduce their exclusive dependence on airport fees and create an additional revenue source that can be reinvested in airport infrastructure development, service enhancements, and expansion of commercial areas².

Thus, although airports are an integral part of the aviation ecosystem, they are also strategic partners in local communities and cities they serve. Airports are inseparably linked to the concept of "*Airport Cities*", a term coined by Prof. John D. Kasarda, an academic and consultant in airport planning and economic development.

The airport city refers to a form of urban development where an airport becomes the focal point of an area or metropolitan area, generating a wide range of economic, social, and commercial activities that develop around it. These "airport cities" combine traditional airport functions like passenger terminals and cargo facilities with various other activities, such as offices, hotels, shopping centers, residential areas, convention centers, and other infrastructures and services³.

The management and development of ancillary activities, therefore, represent a new business opportunity capable of generating extra profits, attracting new stakeholders to the region, and remunerating the investment of shareholders comprising the capital of airport management companies. Retail, therefore, understood as "*retail sales*" in the B2C market, is shifting, especially in airports. It is essential to consider how the trend of traditional retail, referring to physical stores, has undergone a radical change due to the rise of new technologies and the ongoing

² Patrick Lucas, *Non-aeronautical revenues: Diversify and grow*, <https://airport-world.com/non-aeronautical-revenues-diversify-and-grow/>, May 2022

³ Global Airport Cities, *What is an Airport City?*, <http://www.globalairportcities.com/airports-and-partners/what-is-an-airport-city>, 31 January 2012

digital transformation, leading to the advent and consolidation of *e-commerce* or *online stores*, which have fundamentally altered the consumer's retailing process.

In the "*Global Powers of Retailing*" study of 2022 by Deloitte, which annually compiles a ranking of the top 250 global retailers, significant revenue growth was recorded for e-commerce companies such as the American **Amazon (+34.8%)** and the Chinese **Jd.com (+27.6%)**⁴. For this reason, the airport has become a **physical location** where retail is regaining its spaces and market share, as travelers are stimulated through a mandatory path toward boarding. They have more time at their disposal and generally have a more positive and receptive psychological/emotional approach to making purchases.

Airports have evolved from being a "people processing machine" to a "people business"⁵, a more evolved form of non-place defined by Marc Augé. They are no longer

"architectural spaces for transient, public, and impersonal use, intended to be used in the absence of any form of psychological appropriation [...], highly homogenized spaces in which contemporary humans live for significantly long times [...], lacking roots in context, traditions, and history, typical expressions of globalized societies⁶."

Compared to the traditional shopping centers found in all cities, there are some distinct differences in the commercial area of airports that make it a unique environment: firstly, the mandatory path to boarding creates a unique opportunity for stores to capture passengers' attention and encourage them to make purchases during their transit, aided by signage, special offers, and layout. Most international airports, in fact, concentrate almost all the commercial area

⁴ Deloitte, *Global Powers of Retailing 2022, Resilience despite challenges*, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/it/Documents/consumer-business/DeloitteGlobalPowersOfRetailing2022.pdf>

⁵ IATA, *Commercial Non-Aviation Business*, <https://www.iata.org/en/services/consulting/airport-pax-security/airport-commercial-strategy/>

⁶ Marc Augé, *Non-lieux. Introduction à une anthropologie de la surmodernité*, Paris, SEUIL, 1992

(around 85-90% of the total) in the airside part, recognizing this as an industry best practice, unless special circumstances on-site require a broader offering in the landside part⁷.

Secondly, airports unquestionably attract an international audience composed of passengers from different parts of the world, diverse cultures, nationalities, and different spending habits.

Thirdly, there is the limited yet obligatory transit time. Passengers spend a limited amount of time at the airport during their stopovers, creating an opportunity for stores to attract them with targeted offers and promotions.

Ultimately, the mission of some specialized stores in travel-related products (such as luggage, leisure items, travel electronics, books, magazines, and services like currency exchange and souvenir shops) is further emphasized.

The concept of "Airport City," introduced earlier, becomes even stronger to exploit the economic and commercial potential of these places beyond their primary air transportation functions. This enables the creation of integrated and dynamic economic centers that attract businesses, investments, and tourism, generating job opportunities and contributing to local and regional economic development.

"Airport cities" offer multiple advantages, including job creation, investment attraction, improved transportation connections, increased tourism, and stimulation of the local economy. These areas can become true hubs of commercial, financial, and innovative activities, integrating the airport with other industries and economic sectors.

In conclusion, airports have become a fundamental channel in the ongoing retail revolution. Before the advent of the pandemic, the turnover for duty-free alone was estimated to be \$62

⁷ Steer Davies Gleave, *Heathrow Airport - Review of Commercial Revenues*, Final Report for Civil Aviation Authority, https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/docs/33/1563b_H7_Commercial_Revenues_report_by_SDG.pdf, April 2017

billion in 2016, with a forecast to reach \$90 billion by 2023⁸. Additionally, over 6% of "luxury" shopping is conducted within airport terminals (a 4% increase from 2015⁹) and is a growing trend.

With the ongoing pandemic, all non-aviation revenue sources understandably decreased in 2020 compared to 2019. Globally, sources directly affected by passenger volumes suffered the most: retail concessions (-65.2%), aviation catering services (-64.1%), food and beverage (-53.1%), and car parking (-48.9%) recorded the most significant revenue declines in 2020¹⁰.

Source: ACI World, 2022 Airport Key Performance Indicators¹¹

⁸ Credence Research, *Airport Retail Market 2016-2028, Global Industry Size & Forecast*, <https://www.credenceresearch.com/report/airport-retail-market>

⁹ Claudia D’Arpizio, Federica Levato, Daniele Zito, Marc-André Kamel, Joëlle de Montgolfier, *Luxury Goods Worldwide Market Study, Fall-Winter 2016*, <https://www.bain.com/insights/luxury-goods-worldwide-market-study-fall-winter-2016>, 27 December 2016

¹⁰ Patrick Lucas, *Non-aeronautical revenues: Diversify and grow*, <https://airport-world.com/non-aeronautical-revenues-diversify-and-grow/>, May 2022

¹¹ ACI World, *2022 Airport Key Performance Indicators*, <https://store.aci.aero/product/2022-airport-key-performance->

Excluding the incredible collapse in revenues resulting from the global shock generated by the pandemic, non-aviation revenues have historically and continue to constitute a vital component of an airport's income statement and the profits derived from it. Moreover, these sources of income tend to generate higher net profit margins compared to aeronautical revenues.

It is from these data that the entirety of airports, specifically the entire sector of non-aviation business and airport travel retail, has been defined by The Economist as "*the sixth continent*"¹² or, as coined by Luxottica, "*the Formula 1 of retail*".

[indicators/#:~:text=The%202022%20Airport%20Key%20Performance,asset%20productivity%2C%20and%20airport%20operations](#)

¹² The Economist, *The sixth continent*, <https://www.economist.com/business/2014/05/10/the-sixth-continent>, 10 May 2014

Chapter 1: Non-aviation Business: Marketing Strategies Applied to Airports

Types of Non-aviation Business at Airports (Duty Free, Retail, Food, Business Class Lounge, Parking, Rent Car, Hotel, Money Exchange, Transportation)

Since the 1990s, airports around the world have undergone a significant transformation, moving from a perception of airports closely tied to infrastructure and consistent with identifying the airport as *a place solely for travel purposes, to the present consideration that emphasizes the definition of a business aimed at fulfilling the diverse needs of the aerodrome visitor*¹³.

While up until that point, travelers primarily focused on services such as hotels, restaurants, and cultural events, since the new millennium - driven by a series of factors we will soon explore - the international trend has witnessed a strong shift in attention towards consumption: airport shopping has evolved over time, detaching from the typical duty-free price dynamics and has become today an important laboratory of architectural, technological, and commercial innovation.

The evolution of the commercial offerings in travel retail has distinguished itself over time from the traditional market, adapting to the characteristics of the traveling customer who has become the primary focus¹⁴. We must start by analyzing the motivations that lead travelers to the airport. The main motivation is to move from one place to another, crucial to separate activities deemed obligatory for achieving the goal - and consequently not usable in commercial terms - from those considered ancillary and therefore potentially usable for commercial purposes¹⁵.

Therefore, when discussing "airport management", the first major distinction that must be made is between the **aviation sector** - which refers to *all activities related to flight operations and related*

¹³ Vincenzo Fasone, Pasquale Maggiore, *Lo sviluppo della dimensione non-aviation nelle aziende di gestione aeroportuale: evidenze empiriche dal caso GEASAR S.p.A.*, https://www.impresaprogetto.it/sites/impresaprogetto.it/files/articles/2-2011_wp_fasone_maggiore.pdf, 2011-2

¹⁴ Daniele Gregorio, *Da dentro il travel retail: la risorsa Dufry*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

¹⁵ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *La domanda dal Dwell Time evolve. E l'offerta?*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

instrumental services - and the **non-aviation sector**, encompassing *all commercial services offered to passengers within the airport area*¹⁶. The latter now significantly impacts the revenues of airports and does not burden passengers.

In more detail, **aviation activities** include:

- ***Aviation in the strict sense***, i.e., the management, development, and maintenance of centralized infrastructure and airport facilities (Legislative Decree no. 18/1999, Appendix B), services related to aircraft, and airport security.
- ***Handling***, i.e., ground assistance services (Legislative Decree no. 18/1999, Appendix A), related to complementary, accessory, and instrumental commercial activities to the provision of air transport services carried out within the airport, in addition to functional operations carried out both "airside" (such as boarding/disembarking of passengers, baggage and cargo, baggage sorting, parking guidance, and refueling) and in the "passenger area" (check-in, lost & found, ticketing, general information).

Non-aviation activities include:

- ***Travel retail***, the complex of retail activities offered to passengers, operators, and visitors within the airport: shops, bars, restaurants, etc.
- ***Other activities***, carried out both within the airport area (advertising, banks, pharmacies, laundries, hotels, entertainment services, etc.) and outside (car rental and parking management).

Activities not related to the aviation sector are considered instrumental to the airport infrastructure. Hence, despite their objectively commercial nature and entirely private

¹⁶ Il Diritto Amministrativo, Rivista Giuridica, *Il CGARS sul mercato e la concorrenza nelle infrastrutture aeroportuali e il distinguo tra attività c.d. aviation e attività c.d. non aviation*, <https://www.ildirittoamministrativo.it/Il-CGARS-sul-mercato-concorrenza-nelle-infrastrutture-aeroportuali-il-distinguo-tra-attivita%3%A0-non-aviation/ult1002>, Anno XV - n. 06 - June 2023

contractual nature, *these services are considered subject to the general obligation of transparency towards operators in a regime of possible competition*¹⁷.

Furthermore, the management of airport management companies has broad autonomy only over the non-aviation component of the total revenues since, as known, so-called aviation revenues come from fees and charges (landing, take-off, stopover, boarding, disembarking, etc.) defined by the applicable regulations.

Airport management has therefore undergone significant transformation over the years, especially concerning investment methods in the non-aviation sector, which have taken on a strategic role in the revenue model of airport operators, as all industry players have shifted a portion of their business in this direction.

Let's first define what is meant by "**non-aviation business**" - also known as "non-aeronautical business" - to delimit the scope, i.e., *"the structure within the airport capable of generating very high profits and increasing investments in services that were considered ancillary in the past (e.g., parking, hotels, catering, advertising, management of premises, and commercial activities), and are now considered essential by the customer, whose perception of a better offer can generate a greater competitive advantage, ultimately contributing to value creation"*¹⁸.

Non-aviation business activities are highly varied as complementary services to aviation support activities. In a general sense, we can recognize the following macro-categories:

- **Commercial services**, which can be further divided into sales activities (ranging from luxury boutiques and duty-free to tobacco, newspapers, money exchange, and car rental),

¹⁷ Il Diritto Amministrativo, Rivista Giuridica, *Il CGARS sul mercato e la concorrenza nelle infrastrutture aeroportuali e il distinguo tra attività c.d. aviation e attività c.d. non aviation*, <https://www.ildirittoamministrativo.it/Il-CGARS-sul-mercato-concorrenza-nelle-infrastrutture-aeroportuali-il-distinguo-tra-attivita%3%A0-non-aviation/ult1002>, Anno XV - n. 06 - June 2023

¹⁸ Vincenzo Fasone, Pasquale Maggiore, *Lo sviluppo della dimensione non-aviation nelle aziende di gestione aeroportuale: evidenze empiriche dal caso GEASAR S.p.A.*, https://www.impresaprogetto.it/sites/impresaprogetto.it/files/articles/2-2011_wp_fasone_maggiore.pdf, 2011-2

commercial catering services (bars, cafes, restaurants), commercial advertising services, and complementary commercial services (ATMs, but also the sale of local products, pharmacies, internet cafes, and wellness centers).

- **Tourist services**, i.e., the sale of tickets for events, exhibitions, or shows, but also guided tours inside the airport in areas not commonly accessible.
- **Congress services**, renting spaces within the airport for conferences, meetings, or conventions, but also through hotel chains in the airport area.
- **Distributive and property management services**, i.e., real estate activities of entire airport lands and buildings.
- **Consulting services**, i.e., consultancy to support new operators in the realization of their airport infrastructure or to enhance the existing one¹⁹.

In practice, we can classify the following commonly used fields of action:

- Retail activities
 - *Duty-free*
 - *Duty paid*
- Food & beverage (restaurants, bars, cafes)
- Car rental
- Parking
- Management of advertising spaces
- Other activities (which can be related to ticketing services, vehicle maintenance, *real estate*)²⁰

¹⁹ Vincenzo Fasone, Pasquale Maggiore, *Lo sviluppo della dimensione non-aviation nelle aziende di gestione aeroportuale: evidenze empiriche dal caso GEASAR S.p.A.*, https://www.impresaprogetto.it/sites/impresaprogetto.it/files/articles/2-2011_wp_fasone_maggiore.pdf, 2011-2

²⁰ SEA Milan Airports, *Performance Economiche Del Business Non Aviation*, Sustainability Report, <http://dnf2018.seamilano.eu/it/performance-economiche-del-business-non-aviation#>, 2018

The forecasts for the non-aviation sector are extremely positive. A 2018 Statista research on global duty-free and travel retail predicted reaching \$125 billion by 2025²¹.

Going slightly back in time and analyzing data extracted from the 2010 Annual Report of **ACI - Airports Council International**²², i.e., the association of civilian airport operators created in 1991, which now represents 712 members and 1925 airports operating in 171 countries, it is evident that the total airport revenues worldwide in 2009 reached \$95 billion. Of these, 53.5% was represented by the aviation sector and 46.5% by the non-aviation sector, with a 3% increase in the latter compared to the previous year.

Going into more detail on non-aviation revenue, a significant leap was made thanks to the car rental sector (+9%), food and beverage (+7%), and retail (+2%).

Even when focusing on European airports, the same annual report shows the confirmation of the progressively increasing trend of non-aviation in the EU, which reached €12.1 billion (47% of total revenues) in 2009.

²¹ Statista, <https://www.statista.com>

²² ACI - Airport Council International, <https://aci.aero/>

List of Airport Activities for Profit Sources	
Aeronautical	Non-Aeronautical
Landing fees	Duty free and retail
Passenger fees	Food and Beverage
Aircraft parking fees	Car rental
Handling fees	Advertising
Terminal lease fees	Parking
Others (air traffic control fees, lighting fees, airbridge fees)	Charging Services (fuel, water and electricity services, ecc..)
	Others (counseling, visitor and business services, real estate development)

Duty Free Shop: Literally meaning "tax-free shop," it represents a retail store catering to airport travelers that does not apply regular local taxes on the marketed goods, consequently offering the opportunity to purchase branded products at discounted prices.

The duty-free sector is a significant source of revenue for airports and the retailers within. The presence of these shops can attract more passengers inside the airport, increase their dwell time, and consequently enhance revenues for the facility and retailers.

These products, which typically range from alcoholic beverages to perfumes and cosmetics, as well as luxury goods, are not subject to the country's customs duties as they have not truly entered the national territory but are in the "transit" space that enjoys special tax benefits²³.

Duty-free operators obtain a concession from the airport management company through a tender process (usually lasting between 5 and 7 years), where the winner is the one who, based on their estimates of air traffic, passenger types, and airport importance, can offer the highest and most advantageous total sales commission and annual minimum franchise for the airport²⁴.

From this, it is evident that the cost of items is linked to the physical location of the duty-free and the commissions of the respective airport, which is why the same product can have different prices in different duty-free shops.

A report by *researchandmarkets.com* highlighted that the global duty-free market at airports was estimated at \$77.6 billion in 2019²⁵, with a forecasted compound annual growth rate of 6.3% (subsequently drastically reduced due to the COVID-19 pandemic).

Retail Shop: Refers to the extensive range of retail stores and services targeted at passengers in transit or waiting for their flight.

According to a study by Research and Markets, the global airport retail shop market was estimated at around \$46.5 billion in 2019, with a projected compound annual growth rate of 4.2% until 2026 (subsequently drastically reduced due to the COVID-19 pandemic).

Airport retail shops can encompass a wide range of product categories, such as fashion, luxury, accessories, electronics, books, gift items, and much more. The main characteristic is that these

²³ Alessio Ancillao, *Duty-free shops: come funzionano e chi sono i principali operatori*, <https://www.ninjamarketing.it/2012/11/11/duty-free-shops-come-funzionano-e-chi-sono-i-principali-operatori/>, 11 November 2012

²⁴ N26, *Guida ai negozi duty free*, <https://n26.com/it-it/blog/duty-free>, 7 June 2022

²⁵ ResearchAndMarkets.com, *Global Duty-free Retailing Market - Growth, Trends, and Forecast (2020 - 2025)*, <https://www.researchandmarkets.com>, 2022

stores can be owned and operated by individual brands or by specialized retail operators managing multiple stores within the airport.

Luxury products account for about 40% of total sales in the retail shop sector, according to The Moodie Davitt Report's analysis²⁶.

Their strategic location is typically in high-visibility areas, transit zones, and flight waiting areas, aiming to capture passengers' attention and generate sales.

Retail shops were among the first to create a favorable "environment" for purchases through a pleasant experience that includes selecting high-quality products, offers not available outside this context, presenting products attractively, and using technology to enhance the shopping experience.

Food & Beverage: Represents a significant revenue source for airports. Generally, airports offer a wide range of dining options to meet the needs of transit passengers, which can vary considerably depending on the airport's size. This sector primarily comprises international restaurant chains and catering companies, but airports often also offer a mix of "local" restaurants.

The type of dining options also varies, and the offerings at airports cater to all types of clientele, including fast food, bars, cafes, full-fledged restaurants, and even gourmet restaurants and bistros, especially in major hubs or international layover airports.

A notable mention in this category is vending machines, offering snacks and beverages from well-known brands such as Coca-Cola, Pepsi, and Nestlé.

The airport food & beverage sector is continuously evolving and adapting to market trends and needs. Many airport dining companies are becoming increasingly innovative, striving to meet the needs of passengers seeking healthy and sustainable food and beverage options. Some

²⁶ The Moodie Davitt Report, *Luxury products drive airport retail sales growth, with eyewear emerging as key growth category*, <https://www.moodiedavittreport.com>

companies offer foods made with organic and local ingredients, while others aim to reduce the environmental impact of their operations.

Car Rental: Involves the car rental activity conducted inside or in the immediate vicinity of the airport. The activity is managed by international or local car rental companies, offering rental services for various sizes and models of cars, including luxury vehicles. The airport car rental sector is another highly profitable activity, as airports represent the initial destination reached, whether for business or leisure purposes, before moving around independently. Data from a 2019 Statista study reported that the global revenues of airport car rental companies were approximately \$49.4 billion in 2018.

In this domain, too, from a "green" perspective, many operators are striving to innovate and adapt to customer needs by offering services such as electric cars or direct car delivery to the airport.

The global airport car rental market, according to a 2021 study by Research and Markets, is expected to reach an estimated figure of \$63.4 billion by 2027, with a compound annual growth rate of 6.1% from 2021 to 2027²⁷.

Parking: Another significant revenue source for airport operators. Airports offer various parking options for all types of travelers: short-term, long-term, covered parking, uncovered parking, and valet parking services.

According to Allied Market Research, the global airport parking market in 2019, in the pre-pandemic period, was estimated at \$5.2 billion²⁸; COVID-19 led to a 50-70% decrease in annual revenues due to the drastic decline in air travel.

Short-term parking, generally more expensive and paid per hour or fraction of an hour of stay, is typically used by those picking up or travelers needing a short stopover.

²⁷ ResearchAndMarkets.com, *Global Airport Car Rental Market to 2027: Trends, Opportunities and Competitive Analysis*, <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5691734/global-airport-car-rental-market-to-2027>, September 2022

²⁸ Allied Market Research, <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com>

Long-term parking, cheaper with prices calculated based on the days of stay, is intended for travelers leaving their cars at the airport for an extended period.

Covered parking - more expensive than uncovered, which is the most common and economical - is available in some airports and is for those who wish to protect their car from weather conditions or external agents.

Valet parking service, finally, is offered by some airports and allows travelers to hand over their car to a parking attendant who will park it on their behalf, and it is the most expensive among those offered by airports.

Moreover, in recent years, technological innovation has also been influencing the parking sector through digital parking solutions, enabling online reservations and access via QR codes or license plate recognition.

Advertising: Involves promoting products and services through advertising in public spaces at the airport (boarding gates, corridors, baggage claim areas, and other spaces) aimed at transit passengers.

The advertising sector at airports is also becoming increasingly digital, with a 35% increase in digital advertising revenues in 2019 at US airports compared to the previous year²⁹, and most importantly, steadily growing revenues, reaching \$840 million in the USA in 2019, according to a Statista report³⁰.

Advertising can take many forms: billboards, videos, totems, projections, banners, posters, store windows, and dynamic advertising. Airport advertising companies often collaborate with airports to identify available advertising spaces and define the fees for using these spaces.

Furthermore, these spaces are usually used to promote various products and services, including airlines, hotels, restaurants, car rentals, telephone companies, and other travel services.

²⁹ Frances Marcellin, *The digital transformation of airport advertising*, in *Airport Technology*, 2019

³⁰ Statista, <https://www.statista.com>

Travel Retail at Airports: History, Characteristics, Evolution

Travel retail at airports is a concept that has evolved over time, incorporating a range of activities and services that were initially not present but have become crucial, influenced by changing traveler preferences and attitudes.

If we generally refer to "travel retail" as a significant portion of non-aviation business, encompassing all retail activities within a transit location like an airport, we can distinguish three historical phases of its evolution. These phases were notably influenced by international socio-political and economic contexts.

The birth of this industry dates back to 1947, thanks to the vision of entrepreneur Brendan O'Regan in Ireland at Shannon Airport³¹, where the first duty-free shop for passengers in transit to the United States was inaugurated. This event opened up the concept of the extraterritoriality of airport areas, offering a good range of alcohol, tobacco, local products, and soon after, perfumes. From that moment, both in Europe - with Paris and Amsterdam in 1952 and 1958 respectively - and outside Europe, with Panama opening sales of magazines, newspapers, and souvenirs³², the travel retail sector entered its first expansive phase with *duty-free* and *duty-paid*, which continued throughout the 1960s and emerged almost unscathed from the 1970s and the related oil crisis of 1972, which significantly impacted fuel costs and consequently ticket prices.

During this period, despite the global economic crisis, the unstoppable growth of the travel retail sector led to a business that jumped from 450 million to over 2 billion dollars³³. The second phase arrived in 1999 when, within the emerging European Union, the internal European market was established, resulting in the abolition of customs barriers, including the community duty-free system. This brought about a massive change in the airport travel retail system. In this phase, the phenomenon reached approximately 18 billion dollars.

³¹ Padraic Regan, *Flying on course: Public-sector innovation at Shannon airport*, in *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, s.l., IP Publishing, 2017

³² Daniele Gregorio, *Da dentro il travel retail: la risorsa Dufry*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

³³ Daniele Gregorio, *Da dentro il travel retail: la risorsa Dufry*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

Between the second and third phases, another variable slowed down growth: the September 11, 2001 attacks and subsequent airport terrorism alerts in the following years, which reduced "trust" in air transportation. Despite this, the sector continued its expansion, reaching 33 billion dollars in 2007 (including both duty-free and travel retail in the strict sense). This was achieved through operators' reengineering of services based on three main drivers:

1. cost reduction
2. increased efficiency
3. customer-focused approach emphasizing quality³⁴.

From this moment, a decisive shift occurred from a market primarily based on tax exemption (duty-free) to the modern concept of travel retail (understood as retail stores), encompassing luxury brands as well.

The third significant historical phase of change in this industry coincides with the so-called "*democratization of travel*", expanding the concept of a traveler to any social class from any continent. This transformation was influenced by several factors:

- the entry of low-cost airlines into the market
- globalization
- the use of the internet for a new travel perspective

Consequently, both the profile of travelers and the very concept of travel retail evolved. On one hand, the target demographic broadened, becoming younger compared to the previously older average age. On the other hand, there was increased heterogeneity in socio-economic and geographical backgrounds; nationalities that were previously a minority target, such as Russians, Chinese, and Arabs, began to travel more. Consequently, the interests of the audience in terms of purchases and brands, purchasing power, and types of services offered within travel retail also changed. This led to the development of dining options and the sale of local products. Furthermore, there was a focus on luxury fashion brands.

³⁴ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *Marketing ambientale nel travel retail*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

From another general perspective, that of airport management, especially regarding economic activities, Anne Graham³⁵ identifies three key elements in recent decades that have led to a drastic evolution:

- The privatization of airports.
- The expansion of non-aviation-related commercial activities (including travel retail).
- Ownership diversification.

These three aspects, intricately linked, should be seen in the context of the exponential growth of airports internationally and their related maintenance and service expenses, profound modifications in recent decades, efficiency challenges, and the relentless pursuit of generating profits. Financially, the maintenance and modernization of airport infrastructures are understandably costly. According to the International Air Transport Association (IATA), between 2023 and 2030, a total of 1.2 to 1.5 trillion dollars will be spent on infrastructure development³⁶.

In terms of airport company budgets, these factors have demonstrated how non-aviation components have become a structural element within airport revenues in recent decades. Initially regarded as public infrastructure supported by the state and available to third-party users, it has now assumed more corporate characteristics with associated economic constraints of effectiveness and efficiency³⁷. It's worth noting that in 2009, the global airport industry reached a value of 95 billion dollars, with non-aeronautical revenues accounting for 46.5% of the total. This represented a 3% growth from the previous year, driven by an increase in the retail sector (+2%), real estate (+10%), car rental (+9%), and food & beverage³⁸.

³⁵ Anne Graham, *Managing airports. An international perspective*, Oxford, Butterworth-Heinemann, 2008

³⁶ Justin Hayward, *Airport Infrastructure - Everything You Need To Know*, <https://simpleflying.com/airport-infrastructure/>, 12 January 2023

³⁷ Maria Martellini, *Economia e gestione delle imprese aeroportuali*, s.l., Franco Angeli, 2005

³⁸ Vincenzo Fasone, Pasquale Maggiore, *Lo sviluppo della dimensione non-aviation nelle aziende di gestione aeroportuale: evidenze empiriche dal caso GEASAR S.p.A.*, https://www.impresaprogetto.it/sites/impresaprogetto.it/files/articles/2-2011_wp_fasone_maggiore.pdf, 2011-2

Hence, it is evident from this trend that the development of non-aviation business by management companies has become an opportunity to achieve higher levels of productivity. This is due to the evident strong link between these services and the core airport business³⁹.

One of the initial questions to ask is whether these types of infrastructures are publicly or privately managed. In this case, a major distinction needs to be made between the United States and Europe. While in the USA, nearly all major airports are government-managed—either federal or local, such as JFK, La Guardia, Dallas-Fort Worth, Las Vegas McCarran, and many others—in Europe, a trend toward privatized management has emerged, with minority government involvement (e.g., Rome Fiumicino, Copenhagen, and Zurich) or public management but with private company participation (e.g., Paris Charles De Gaulle, Amsterdam Schiphol, Madrid Barajas). In the UK, many airports are entirely managed by private companies, like London Heathrow, following the privatization implemented by the British government in 1987.

However, whether privately or government-managed, government authorities still regulate airports in the aviation sector through specific government bodies, given the complexity of the structures and operations. At the international level, there is the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO)⁴⁰, responsible for *promoting the adoption of international standards and conventions in air navigation, passenger and cargo transport, and aviation transport safety*.

A specific focus is required to analyze the management of Italian airports from a legislative point of view, and the respective tasks assigned to the airport manager. Until 1993, Italy had three types of management for civil airports, which can be briefly summarized as follows:

1. Direct management by the state (the state creates and provides for the maintenance of assets and infrastructure at its own expense, in addition to managing the airport, and collects the revenues).

³⁹ Tae Oum, Chunyan Yu, Xiaowen Fu, *A comparative analysis of productivity performance of the world's major airports: summary report of the ATRS global airport benchmarking research report—2002*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Vol. 9, September 2003

⁴⁰ ICAO - International Civil Aviation Organization, www.icao.int

2. Partial management (granting of state-owned land, while infrastructure management remained the responsibility of the state).
3. Total management (the concessionaire was given complete management of all services within the airport, including infrastructure).

With the reform of the airport system in 1993 (Law No. 537/2012), the state indicated the total management model as the prevalent concessionary regime. This led to the establishment of a capital company to manage the services and infrastructures of the airports, which were partly managed by the state. The goal was to promote the progressive privatization of Italian airports to be managed on entrepreneurial bases⁴¹.

According to Article 705 of the Navigation Code⁴², the airport manager is:

"The subject entrusted, under the control and supervision of ENAC [...] with the task of administering and managing, according to criteria of transparency and non-discrimination, airport infrastructures and coordinating and controlling the activities of the various private operators present in the airport or in the considered airport system."

The role of travel retail - and more generally the non-aviation sector - becomes a fundamental value creator for airport management, resulting in a complete reconfiguration of the place and the very concept of an airport.

⁴¹ AVCP - Autorità per la Vigilanza sui Contratti Pubblici di Lavori, Servizi e Forniture, *La gestione aeroportuale*, <https://www.anticorruzione.it/documents/91439/211723/La+Gestione+Aeroportuale.pdf/763996fe-3a5d-a7c5-b414-8f3019d083d1?t=1585298355383>, March 2013

⁴² ENAC - Ente Nazionale per l'Aviazione Civile, *Articolo 705 (Compiti del gestore aeroportuale)*, <https://www.enac.gov.it/la-normativa/normativa-nazionale/codice-della-navigazione/articolo-705>, 12 March 2018

Customer Journey and Dwell Time: From Airport Arrival to the Gate

In a location like the airport, especially in the related travel retail areas, the concept of time takes on a fundamental role. Firstly, because it's a "temporary" place where the traveler is "transient" and awaiting departure. Secondly, in the time available, the traveler has an almost obligatory path to follow between necessary operations and downtime, all while undergoing a constantly changing emotional process.

This timeframe, from the moment of arrival at the airport to boarding the plane, has a precise definition, known as the "*customer journey*" which, from a marketing perspective, Philip Kotler translates as:

"[...] the whole set of experiences that customers have during their relationship with an organization, from the moment they become aware of the company until they end the relationship⁴³."

Applied to the airport concept, this definition frames the customer journey as the mapping of all the stages through which the passenger interacts with the infrastructure, up to departure. This mapping process allows the identification of key moments where the passenger can have a positive or negative experience, enabling airport management companies to design interventions to enhance the customer experience and, in the realm of non-aviation, to stimulate purchases.

Although retail locations generally share common characteristics, the airport is characterized by many differences in both the environment and the shopping journey. These can be summarized into three factors:

1. **Time Available:** The timing of the airside phase, i.e., after security checks, is a variable beyond the passenger's control. According to Bohl (2014), in a situation like that of the airport, where there's limited and defined time available for shopping, time influences purchases. Various studies demonstrate a link between dwell time and sales, with 50% of all purchases occurring within 30 minutes of passengers entering the commercial area.

⁴³ Philip Kotler, *Marketing Insights from A to Z: 80 Concepts Every Manager Needs to Know*, s.l., Wiley, 2003

2. **Walking Distance in the Terminal:** Unlike traditional retail spaces where consumers try to take the shortest path between stores, in the airport, passengers are obliged to cover great distances, traversing various areas with shops offering diverse options. This leads to experiences like "happy hour shopping" (Crawford & Melewar, 2003; Omar & Kent, 2001) and visiting multiple stores "to kill time."
3. **Human Crowding:** This refers to the psychological stress experienced due to the perception of too many people in a confined space (measured through the objective variable of density), which also influences purchase intention. In the realm of airport retail, the concept of human crowding manifests at two levels:
 - a. **Store Crowding:** The number of people inside the same store; the presence of other potential consumers can generate positive emotions, as individuals tend to follow the behaviors of fellow consumers.
 - b. **Airport Crowding:** The total number of people at the airport; the quantity of people at the airport could be perceived as positive for sales⁴⁴, especially if a balanced level of crowding is achieved, not causing congestion and subsequently not increasing psychological stress. Overcrowding, in fact, can have the opposite effect, creating a sense of risking missing the flight.

To mitigate the effects of human crowding in airports, management companies employ various strategies, ranging from organizing passenger flow to increasing common spaces, using technology to improve flow management, and implementing comfort and entertainment services. Additionally, many airport retail companies focus on enhancing the customer experience in these areas by offering comfortable seating, relaxation areas, food and beverage services, and entertainment. Some airports have even added facilities such as karaoke, pools, golf facilities, and saunas to make the airport dwell time more pleasant, thus transforming the

⁴⁴ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

passenger into a shared customer of both the airline and the airport, establishing an inseparable commercial relationship between the two⁴⁵.

Shopping at the airport occurs in a context rich with signals reminding the consumer of the main objective of their presence, which is to catch a flight. Therefore, the absolute distinction between classic retail and travel retail lies in the uniqueness of the location, possessing a set of characteristic factors that influence purchasing behavior: destinations, time available, flight delays⁴⁶.

It's important to highlight that compared to other environments, airport travel retail has stable characteristics such as uniformity in the motivation for the visit and the aspect of average time. However, it also has variable and very complex elements such as socio-cultural and geographical disparities. These make the marketing strategy unique: specificity is the crucial element to consider, capable of impacting seemingly disjointed strategies, such as the use of color in store environments⁴⁷.

An airport and an airport retail experience that fulfills passengers' desires in terms of a "sense of place" and fosters the right emotions, even through a more personalized and technological experience, inevitably increases propensity to purchase. To achieve this, it's necessary to first identify and recognize the target audience and accordingly tailor the retail experience⁴⁸.

Some studies⁴⁹ have attempted to analyze the passenger's journey from airport arrival to boarding, such as the case of Rome Airports for a passenger taking a flight to a destination outside of Europe.

⁴⁵ Vincenzo Fasone, Lukas Kofler, Raffaele Scuderi, *Business performance of airports: non aviation revenues and their determinants*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Vol. 53, June 2016

⁴⁶ Peter Mohn, *The shopping experience – it has to be omni...*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁴⁷ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *Marketing ambientale nel travel retail*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

⁴⁸ Peter Mohn, *The shopping experience – it has to be omni...*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁴⁹ Fulvio Fassone, *Aeroporto: i tempi del passeggero e il tempo degli acquisti*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

The passenger used approximately 30 minutes in total for check-in, passport control, and security checks. Considering the boarding time as fixed, the more time is spent on this obligatory process, the less time will be available for shopping or consumption experiences at the airport. Even this step at Rome Fiumicino Airport has been optimized in recent years in terms of timing through the use of e-gates for passport control and reduction of security check times.

The research then analyzed if the available time has a direct correlation with the propensity to make purchases. In the time range from 0 to 3 hours, this correlation,

relative to the ratio between spending per passenger and time (referred to as *Sppax*), is significantly high and steadily increasing. In the subsequent time fraction, from 3 to 7 hours, there is a slowing of the curve, although it remains positive. The saturation point, beyond which the impact on total revenue is minimal, is identifiable at around 3.5 hours⁵⁰.

Source: Aeroporti di Roma⁵¹

The airport customer journey can be divided into two distinct moments:

⁵⁰ Fulvio Fassone, *Aeroporto: i tempi del passeggero e il tempo degli acquisti*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁵¹ ADR - Aeroporti di Roma, <https://www.adr.it>

1. **Landside:** This refers to the time spent on the landside, encompassing the period before security and customs checks. The landside area, dedicated to pre-flight activities, is also accessible to accompanying individuals who may not necessarily be traveling.
2. **Airside:** This pertains to the time spent on the airside, the phase with the highest potential interest for travel retail activities, available to passengers after completing customs and boarding procedures. The airside areas are accessible only to passengers holding the necessary flight departure documents⁵².

In both moments, passengers engage in two types of activities:

1. **Process activities:** These are mandatory operations necessary for boarding, each with a defined time period and potential to induce stress (arrival at the airport on time, check-in, passport control, and security checks).
2. **Discretionary (or voluntary) activities:** These are activities chosen by the passenger and are influenced by emotional variables.

Passengers are still required to arrive early to complete process operations; hence, the time between entering the airport and departure has increased significantly in recent years, favoring discretionary activities.

Unlike consumers in a typical retail environment, passengers go through what is known as the "travel stress curve" (Scholvinck, 2000) representing the initial phase. They then reach the discretionary activities phase, which is seen as "happy hour shopping" for airport retailers, characterized by impulse or unplanned purchases (Crawford & Melewar, 2003)⁵³.

According to a study by Cheng-Lung Wu and Yimeng Chen, two critical strategic characteristics that influence airport retail are:

⁵² Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *La domanda dal Dwell Time evolve. E l'offerta?*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁵³ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

1. **Passenger Dwell Time in the Terminal:** This refers to the impact of the free time spent in the terminal waiting for boarding on the likelihood of making a purchase.
2. **Terminal Layout:** The physical characteristics of the shopping environment that can influence a traveler's spending decisions, such as perfume, colors used, music, store location, and terminal size.

This brings forth the concept of "Dwell Time," which is related to waiting times and has slightly different interpretations depending on the context. However, in recent years, it has gained significant importance in the travel retail sector, particularly in large infrastructures like airports, due to its substantial impact on purchasing motivation among the "captive audience"⁵⁴.

From the passenger's perspective, it refers to the wait times for transportation services that motivated their presence in the particular infrastructure. It encompasses the various elements affecting the overall travel time: wait times for boarding, baggage handling, and transfers between different modes of transportation⁵⁵.

In the specific case of the airport, dwell time is related to the value of the obligatory time spent by the consumer in an area with shops, restaurants, and other services:

*"the consumer's time spent in an area featuring shops and restaurants,
as reported by the consumer on exit"⁵⁶*

This applies to both landside and airside phases, with a more pronounced effect in the latter.

⁵⁴ The concept of "captive audience" is related to marketing, where an audience is compelled or obliged to remain in a specific place or situation, having limited or no options to avoid or ignore the message or information being presented to them.

In the context of airports, this concept relates to a location where the displayed average prices are higher than usual, precisely because it's a mandatory route.

⁵⁵ Iolanda Conte, *Il Dwell time nelle infrastrutture: integrare reti e livelli di servizio*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁵⁶ Patrick Bohl, *The impact of airport shopping environments and dwell time on consumer spending*, *Vezetéstudomány / Budapest Management Review*, 2014, http://unipub.lib.uni-corvinus.hu/1738/1/vt_2014n11p11.pdf

Source: *Alison Livingstone, Vesna Popovic, Ben Kraal, Philip J.Kirk, Understanding the Airport Passenger Landside Retail Experience*⁵⁷

This is because, during the first phase (landside), mandatory operations like check-in, passport control, and security checks generate a stressful emotional impact. Simultaneously, the passenger's desire is to get through these quickly. In contrast, the second phase (airside) is the moment when there's a peak of pleasure due to the adrenaline drop after successfully completing the main process activities. This phase is perceived as an empty moment to fill with recreational activities⁵⁸.

Additionally, another consideration arises: while in the landside phase, dwell time is fragmented into various moments—between arrival at the airport and check-in, between check-in and security checks—in the airside phase, dwell time is a single, continuous time block that extends up to boarding. This is the most crucial time window for non-aviation business and travel retail in particular. Even though during landside, there might still be accompanying individuals

⁵⁷ Alison Livingstone, Vesna Popovic, Ben Kraal, Philip J.Kirk, *Understanding the Airport Passenger Landside Retail Experience*, <https://dl.designresearchsociety.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2440&context=drs-conference-papers>, Bangkok (Thailand), 2012

⁵⁸ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *La domanda dal Dwell Time evolve. E l'offerta?*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

positively influencing the propensity to purchase in bars or restaurants, it's the commercial activities in the airside that are most effective in terms of sales.

Source: Alison Livingstone, Vesna Popovic, Ben Kraal, Philip J.Kirk, Understanding the Airport Passenger Landside Retail Experience

Empirical data⁵⁹ indeed show that the airport dwell time can be divided into 32% for the landside phase and the remaining 68% for the airside phase.

Patrick Bohl's study on the impact of airport shopping areas and dwell time on purchasing propensity has revealed that "*shopping to kill time*⁶⁰" is one of the main motivations cited for purchases at the airport. More available time also increases the likelihood of spending more. Various analyses demonstrate a positive relationship between purchases—both sequential and spontaneous—with both available time and walking distances. It is crucial to encourage

⁵⁹ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *La domanda dal Dwell Time evolve. E l'offerta?*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁶⁰ Gerry Crawford, T.C. Melewar, *The importance of impulse purchasing behaviour in the international airport environment*, in *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 2003

passengers to traverse the retail area. The design and layout of the airport area dedicated to retail towards departure gates hold strategic value in generating purchase engagement⁶¹.

Fasone, Kofler, and Scuderi identify twelve hypotheses⁶² that influence non-aviation revenue sources for airports and the variables that can impact their financial performance:

1. **Airport Size:** Larger airports have more opportunities to generate non-aviation revenue due to higher passenger presence and the ability to host a greater variety of commercial activities.
2. **Airport Type:** Hub and destination airports can generate higher non-aviation revenue compared to smaller airports.
3. **Competitiveness:** Airports in highly competitive markets need to diversify their commercial activities.
4. **Regulation:** National legislation can influence an airport's ability to generate non-aviation revenue.
5. **Passenger Type:** Business class passengers are more likely to spend on commercial activities compared to leisure passengers.
6. **Flight Length:** Long-haul flights positively impact luxury product purchases, while short-haul flights positively impact mass consumption product purchases.
7. **Destinations:** The number of available destinations at an airport positively affects commercial activities.
8. **Flag Carriers:** Flag carrier airlines can influence passengers' choice of destination airport, thus positively impacting non-aviation revenue.
9. **Geographical Location:** The presence of airports in areas with a high tourism propensity increases non-aviation revenue.
10. **Airport Space Management:** Effective airport space management directly correlates with increased non-aviation revenue.

⁶¹ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

⁶² Vincenzo Fasone, Lukas Kofler, Raffaele Scuderi, *Business performance of airports: non aviation revenues and their determinants*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Vol. 53, June 2016

11. **Service Quality:** High-quality services can influence passengers' choice to spend more time in the commercial area, resulting in revenue benefits.
12. **Service Variety:** The presence of a variety of services, from relaxation to entertainment, luxury shopping to food and beverage, can influence passengers' decision to spend more time at the airport.

Let's see the passengers' journey from their entrance to the airport until boarding in a schematic way, to have a clear overview of the phases and stimuli encountered:

1. Firstly, **parking:** in 2018, the average cost of a week of parking internationally was \$98 (Heathrow being the most expensive at about \$249/week).
2. Then there is **check-in:** passengers still arrive well in advance at the airport compared to flight departure (Business Insider mentions an international average of 2 hours and 17 minutes), but the technology adopted in recent years has sped up both check-in and security checks through digital kiosks, consequently encouraging travelers to spend more time in the commercial areas of the airside.
3. After the security check, there is the "**recomposure**" area, a small quiet zone where passengers have time to retrieve their phones, wallets, and regroup: it is a "psychological strategy" aimed at reducing stress levels due to checks and making passengers more inclined to shop.
4. The first area encountered in the airside is the **duty-free**, a mandatory passage to reach the boarding gate. For example, structurally at Heathrow airport, pedestrian paths in the duty-free veer left, as this allows much more space for shopping on the right side of the path⁶³: according to consultancy firm *Intervistas*, this generates higher revenues because most people are right-handed and spend more time looking to the right. Furthermore, as seen earlier, duty-free means that foreign taxes on goods are removed, but this does not necessarily mean that the products are cheaper (it may be for heavily taxed products like alcohol or cigarettes, but not for products like toys, electronics, and even food, which

⁶³ Steve Cameron, *Sneaky Ways Airports Get You To Spend Money*, <https://www.businessinsider.com/airports-spend-more-money-duty-free-shopping-restaurants-2019-8?r=US&IR=T>, 2019

generally have a higher overall retail price). Duty-free is a massive sector, valued at over \$67 billion in 2018 according to the Coherent Market Insights report.

5. After duty-free, you enter the **main shopping area** with many options for eating and spending. In this area, there are many strategically positioned signs indicating the time it takes to reach the gates, which serve a psychological purpose in keeping the passenger's stress level low: if, in fact, passengers increase satisfaction by 1%, airport sales increase by 1.5%⁶⁴. The layout of the shops, signage, and attractive displays are designed to maximize the visibility and appeal of the products on display. Additionally, promotions and special offers along the way can further encourage passengers to make purchases. This feature of the mandatory route in airports makes the commercial area a highly visible and accessible environment for passengers. Even those who might not be intentionally looking for products can be influenced by the displays, advertisements, and the atmosphere of the shops along the route. In this area, restaurants are also designed with large windows, relaxing music, and "open" retail points to keep satisfaction and willingness to spend high, but with prices higher than the average: for example, according to The Points Guy magazine, at Los Angeles Airport, there is an average 18% increase in food prices compared to establishments outside the airport. The elevated prices are partly due to the fact that airport restaurants pay a high monthly rent compared to the average outside. To offset the high rents, in recent years, there has been a transformation of airport restaurants becoming more elaborate: not only fast-food chains but also steakhouses, burger joints, proper restaurants, in addition to cocktail bars and oyster clubs.
6. Once the departure gate is announced, the passenger heads to the **boarding gate**, and during the long walk through the terminal, they pass shops set up with diagonal patterns to display all the goods present. The aisles of these shops are very wide to allow for baggage passage, and here too the prices are inflated - again due to the high monthly rent, which in some cases leads to an increase of up to 200% for a bottle of water.

⁶⁴ US Global Investors, <https://www.usfunds.com>

7. In this last stretch before boarding, there is often also a **currency exchange** available, but with a higher exchange rate compared to the outside, ranging from 10% to 26% (source: Investopedia), excluding service charges.
8. When the passenger arrives at the boarding gate, there are still the *last-minute shops*.

The airport passenger: profiling and segmentation

From a marketing perspective, when we talk about the airport passenger, we need to analyze a series of elements that make both the place and the audience unique: we can indeed speak of a "*captive customer audience*"⁶⁵, to use a strong term that represents a target of potential customers who are "obliged" to spend time in a specific place (commercial area) while waiting for boarding.

As mentioned earlier, the entry of low-cost airlines into the market, and the possibility of traveling at low prices - along with a series of strategic factors - has led to the democratization of travel, resulting in an expansion of the target audience in terms of demographics, socio-economic factors, and geography. The airport thus becomes one of the main places for shopping; not surprisingly, in recent years, major industrial groups in the fashion and restaurant sectors have significantly increased their presence inside airports. This evolution has created a new target audience for travel retail with fairly broad characteristics:

- Greater price sensitivity
- More varied socio-cultural background
- Lowering of the average age (while simultaneously widening the age range)
- Audience heterogeneity, with the inclusion of Russians, Chinese, and Arabs
- Broadening of shopping interest sectors⁶⁶.

In more detail, the growth of certain product categories follows the segmentation of airport customers, which is becoming increasingly polarized between low-cost flight passengers - a steadily growing segment - and the increased influx of passengers to and from non-European destinations. The latter, although representing a minority share of the overall passenger volume,

⁶⁵ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

⁶⁶ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *Marketing ambientale nel travel retail*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

generate significant revenues across all airports due to their purchasing power, sometimes up to fifty times higher than that of passengers on domestic routes⁶⁷.

While it's true that from one perspective this "environment" can benefit from the positive emotional state of the passenger that encourages shopping, from another perspective, the breadth of the target audience makes it very complex to identify a valid ad hoc marketing strategy. Traditionally, the literature indicates that passengers of low-cost airlines spend more on commercial services offered at airports compared to other types of passengers, especially focusing on catering services due to the lack of complimentary meals or snacks during the flight⁶⁸.

On this subject, a primary macro distinction in the context of shopping behavior in airport areas is proposed by Andrea Belardini between two types of passengers: the "business" traveler, associated with premium airlines, generally undertaking intercontinental flights, and the "leisure" traveler, associated with low-cost or short/medium-haul airlines, typically traveling for leisure purposes.

⁶⁷ Fulvio Fassone, David Jarach, *Travel retail aeroportuale 2017, prime indicazioni*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, January - April 2018

⁶⁸ Anne Graham, *Managing airports: an international perspective*, 4th edition, s.l., Routledge, 2013

<i>Tipologia</i>	<i>Caratteristiche</i>	<i>Domanda</i>	<i>Assieme</i>
<i>Business</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poco tempo - Alto livello di stress - Buona conoscenza dell'aeroporto 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edicole e librerie - Elettronica - Vestiario - Articoli da regalo - Articoli per la persona - Ristorazione veloce - Ristoranti con servizio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soli - Colleghi
<i>Leisure, Vfr (Visiting Friends and Relatives)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Buon umore - Molto tempo - Ansia relativa agli acquisti - Scarsa conoscenza dell'aeroporto 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edicole e librerie - Prodotti per la cura della persona - Farmacie - Accessori - Souvenir - Ristorazione tipica del luogo 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soli - Coppie - Famiglie - Amici

Source: Belardini 2009

With this initial distinction by passenger type, Belardini attempts to identify a series of generalized purchase characteristics and attitudes. The "business" traveler, accustomed to traveling for work, minimizes airport dwell time and uses it to continue work activities or communicate with colleagues. They limit their free time to purchasing necessities or quickly looking for gifts or souvenirs for family.

On the other hand, the "leisure" traveler typically flies low-cost, often with friends or family, and primarily for pleasure. They are in a good mood and have more time available, making them inclined to make purchases⁶⁹.

⁶⁹ Carlo Maria Lolli Ghetti, *Marketing ambientale nel travel retail*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

However, recent literature reveals in-depth studies indicating that purchases by low-cost passengers are lower compared to other passenger types, as they target a market segment sensitive to price⁷⁰.

Patrick Bohl, for example, identified twelve variables influencing travelers' consumption within airport facilities, which can be the starting point for analysis:

1. Travel type: The purpose of the trip (business or leisure) can influence travelers' spending behavior in airport commercial areas.
2. Traveler type: Refers to spending preferences and habits, which can vary based on travelers' demographic, cultural, and economic characteristics (age, gender, income, etc.).
3. Arrival and departure times: Flight schedules can influence the time travelers spend at the airport and, consequently, their spending behavior.
4. Length of stay at the airport: Relates to the concept of dwell time; generally, travelers who spend more time at the airport tend to spend more than those with short stays.
5. Availability of time: Travelers with time available (dwell time) in the airport's commercial areas tend to spend more on entertainment and dining activities, linking to the concept of "*to kill the time*".
6. Availability of money: That is, spending capacity.
7. Availability of credit: Credit cards—or electronic payments in general—can encourage travelers to spend.
8. Perception of price: The perception of encountering unique offers, deals, or cost-effectiveness influences purchasing behavior.
9. Perception of quality: In this case, the perception of encountering a quality or luxury product influences behavior, especially when connected to the previous point.

⁷⁰ Muneki Yokomi, Phill Wheat, Jun Mizutani, *The impact of low cost carries on non-aeronautical revenues in airport: an empirical study of UK airports*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2017

10. Familiarity with the airport: Being familiar with the airport structure, or having been there before, creates emotional confidence and a propensity to purchase in travelers' choice of stores and services.
11. Availability of information: Having detailed information about the presence of shops and services through commercial area maps.
12. Purchase motivation: The motivations that drive travelers to make purchases can influence their spending behavior⁷¹.

In terms of motivations driving purchases, it's worth highlighting Yi-Shih Chung's study, which distinguishes four types:

1. **Functional motivation:** Pertains to tangible aspects such as product variety, quality, and price.
2. **Social motivation:** Reflects the need to communicate with others who share similar interests, affiliate with peer groups, and interact with sellers.
3. **Experiential motivation:** Relates to the need for sensory stimulation and pleasant experiences.
4. **Travel-related motivation:** Motivations linked to travel, such as buying souvenirs or disposing of residual foreign currency⁷².

The dominant motivation for airport shopping appears to be linked to impulse buying, which accounts for approximately 70% of the total (Crawford and Melewar, 2003), primarily due to the reasons "to fill in time" and "to find a particular product" (Baron and Wass, 2006)⁷³.

⁷¹ Patrick Bohl, *Passenger Shopping Behavior and Purchase Decisions in Airport Retailing: A Typology of Travelers*, in *Journal of Travel Research*, 2011

⁷² Yishih Chung, Wan-Erh Chiang, Cheng-Lung Wu, *Air passengers' shopping motivation and information seeking behaviour*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2013

⁷³ Patrick Bohl, *Towards a dynamic model of airport shopping behaviour*, in *Tudományos Próbapálya*, 2013

Furthermore, a significant study by Cheng-Lung Wu and Yimeng Chen distinguishes three categories of factors influencing airport retail revenues:

- 1) **Passenger characteristics:** These characteristics have a significant impact on revenues and can be further distinguished into:
 - a) Individual purchasing preferences
 - b) Socio-demographic aspects such as age, gender, nationality, and income
 - c) Nature of travel, such as travel motivation, frequency, use of low-cost carriers, and dwell time at the airport;
- 2) **Passenger dwell time in the terminal:** The impact that the free time spent in the terminal while waiting for boarding can have on the likelihood of making a purchase.
- 3) **Terminal layout:** The physical characteristics of the shopping environment, which can influence the traveler's spending decisions, such as perfume, colors used, music, as well as the store location and terminal size.

While the latter two points were addressed in the previous paragraph and more directly concern the customer journey, the first aspect needs to be further explored in this phase. Individual characteristics of each passenger can have different levels of impact on airport retail revenue. Therefore, market segmentation is crucial from the perspective of retail business development, marketing, and pricing⁷⁴.

Two very important studies in this field develop a classification of airport customers—the so-called "airport shoppers"—based on passenger characteristics: the study by Geuens, Vantomme, and Brengman (2004) identifies three groups:

⁷⁴ Cheng-Lung Wu, Chen Yimeng, *Effects of passenger characteristics and terminal layout on airport retail revenue: an agent-based simulation approach*, in *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 2019

- **Apathetic Shoppers:** Those not interested in shopping and go directly to the boarding gate or rest.
- **Mood Shoppers:** Mainly men, impulsive, influenced, and stimulated to purchase by the environment.
- **Shopping Lovers:** Mostly women stimulated by impulsive purchases, with a clear preference for larger stores near the boarding gate⁷⁵.

To these three identified groups, the subsequent study by Chung, Wu, and Chiang (2013) adds a fourth, the "**Traditional Shoppers**", who tend to plan shopping in advance and are more rational in spending⁷⁶.

Gender is also a key factor for segmentation in the airport travel retail market, primarily due to substantial differences in purchasing behavior and choice of purchase. While women are more inclined towards shopping than men (Baron and Wass, 1996), particularly for cosmetic products, clothing, shoes, and accessories, men are more attracted to electronics, brand names, and sportswear (Perng, Chow, Liao, 2010)⁷⁷.

Building upon the theory of shopping momentum⁷⁸, the study by Creed, Ning Shen, Ashill, and Wu expands the analysis of airport shopping in three aspects:

⁷⁵ Maggie Geuens, Delphine Vantomme, Malaika Brengman, *Developing a typology of airport shoppers*, in *Tourism Management*, 2004

⁷⁶ Yishih Chung, Wan-Erh Chiang, Cheng-Lung Wu, *Air passengers' shopping motivation and information seeking behaviour*, in *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 2013

⁷⁷ Cheng-Lung Wu, Chen Yimeng, *Effects of passenger characteristics and terminal layout on airport retail revenue: an agent-based simulation approach*, in *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 2019

⁷⁸ *The Shopping Momentum Theory (SM)* is a marketing technique utilized by airport retail companies to increase sales. The main objective of this strategy is to capitalize on passengers' shopping momentum at the airport, i.e., the moment when they are inclined to purchase products and have free time.

This technique involves positioning airport retail companies strategically along the passengers' mandatory path to capture their attention during transit and encourage purchases.

1. Investigating nuances of consumer purchasing behavior to explore the concept of momentum.
2. Using a new set of more in-depth variables, especially the effects of time availability, crowding, payment type, offers, product type, and involvement in sequential purchasing.
3. Delving into shopping behavior at the airport, an environment that represents a unique situation often created by momentary conditions⁷⁹.

Airport travel retail is primarily influenced by passengers' feelings of excitement and positive emotions, encouraging impromptu purchases that settle at around 70% of the total (Crawford and Melewar, 2003).

Market research provides interesting insights into store life and the relationship between the retailer and the clientele. At the European level, about 60% of customers are under 40 years old, 70% travel for vacation, 23% are habitual buyers, and 77% are occasional. Moreover, the main motivation for purchases is product quality, followed by the brand. 60% of purchases are for themselves, 30% for gifts, and 10% for desired items⁸⁰.

Regarding purchasing methods, a study conducted in 2016 at Dubai International Airport showed that over 50% of purchases are made with credit cards, with the average spending of these customers being 2.7 times higher than that of a cash-paying customer⁸¹.

The SM strategy can be implemented through a series of actions, such as the use of attractive shop displays, special offers and promotions, the presence of friendly and available sales staff, organizing events and entertainment activities, distributing free samples, and more.

This strategy is particularly effective as airport passengers, according to various studies, often have a higher inclination to make purchases compared to customers visiting stores outside the airport.

⁷⁹ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

⁸⁰ Daniele Gregorio, *Da dentro il travel retail: la risorsa Dufry*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, September - December 2016

⁸¹ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

At the same time, the concept of a "travel group" also has a strong inclination to make purchases, albeit with different characteristics. For example, the group moves much more slowly within the terminal due to the presence—sometimes—of children, focusing much more on food and beverage⁸².

Another important area of investigation in a commercial environment like the airport, which is unique in its kind, is the concept of "*sequential purchasing*", i.e., the passenger's motivation to make multiple purchases in that timeframe. Creed B., Ning Shen K., Ashill N., and Wu T. identify four characteristics based on a study conducted at Dubai International Airport regarding the travel journey and purchasing behavior of passengers:

1. When sequential purchasing occurred, it happened within a short timeframe (8 minutes for the 1st quartile).
2. There is a positive relationship between sequential purchasing and both available time and distances walked. Therefore, encouraging passengers to traverse the retail area is important. The design and layout of the airport retail area towards departure gates hold strategic value in generating purchasing engagement.
3. The existing positive relationship between store crowding and instances of sequential purchasing suggests that it is in the retailer's interest to encourage store presence.
4. High involvement in the purchase of the first product has a positive impact on sequential purchasing⁸³.

⁸² Michael Schultz, Christian Schulz, Hartmut Fricke, *Passenger Dynamics at Airport Terminal Environment*, in *Pedestrian and Evacuation Dynamics 2008*, 2009

⁸³ Bernard Creed, Kathy Ning Shen, Nick Ashill, Tianshi Wu, *Retail shopping at airports: Making travellers buy again*, in *Journal of Business Research*, 2021

Chapter 2: Practical Cases of Non-Aviation Business and Comparisons

In this chapter, we will analyze two major international airports that differ in terms of revenues but share a common ground—strategically developing distinct characteristics of the non-aviation business sector. This development primarily stems from the profiling of their respective audiences and, importantly, from the inherent features of the airport based on geographical, political, and economic aspects.

With many revenue streams directly linked to passenger traffic, airport operators are exploring ways to diversify their income streams. Although integral to the aviation ecosystem, these facilities are also strategic partners in local communities and the cities they serve. Properties can be commercially developed in various forms, such as offices, hotels, entertainment and conference centers, outlet stores, and cargo/logistics facilities⁸⁴. This concept is closely tied to "*Airport Cities*⁸⁵", a term coined by Prof. John D. Kasarda, an academic and consultant in airport planning and economic development, to describe how airport terminals have evolved into sophisticated revenue engines featuring various commercial entities.

“Airports no longer serve merely as transport gateways; they have become multi-functional infrastructure. Among non-aeronautical developments,

⁸⁴ Patrick Lucas, *Non-aeronautical revenues: Diversify and grow*, <https://airport-world.com/non-aeronautical-revenues-diversify-and-grow/>, May 2022

⁸⁵ The concept of "*airport cities*" refers to a form of urban development in which an airport becomes the focal point of a zone or metropolitan area, generating a wide range of economic, social, and commercial activities that develop around it. These "airport cities" are characterized by a combination of traditional airport functions, such as passenger terminals and cargo facilities, and a variety of other activities, including offices, hotels, shopping centers, residential areas, conference centers, and other infrastructure and services.

The underlying idea of "airport cities" is to leverage the economic and commercial potential of airports beyond their primary air transport functions. This approach allows for the creation of integrated and dynamic economic centers that attract businesses, investments, and tourism, generating job opportunities and contributing to local and regional economic development.

"Airport cities" offer multiple advantages, including job creation, investment attraction, improved transportation connections, increased tourism, and stimulation of the local economy. These areas can become true hubs for commercial, financial, and innovative activities, integrating the airport with other industries and economic sectors.

retail and food & beverage activities play a crucial role in contributing to airport revenues. Substantial investments have been made to transform airports into shopping centers with various dining options. Additionally, many airports are exploring the online business and developing their e-commerce platforms⁸⁶”.

It has been observed that airport shoppers have unique buying behaviors within a captured environment (e.g., the terminal), different from traditional shoppers. Therefore, an airport's good design that creates a comfortable shopping environment for passengers is a significant advantage. Moreover, passengers' moods and shopping experiences can be easily influenced by time constraints, space limitations, and psychological stress during check-in and immigration procedures.

Research has shown that planned buyers are more inclined toward online shopping, while impulse buyers prefer shopping in physical stores. Although many academic studies have found impulse buying to be the main behavior of buyers, recent marketing research indicates a shift, with pre-planned purchases gaining prominence, especially in the Asian market. Hence, airport e-commerce has significant potential to generate additional non-aeronautical revenues for airports. Many airports are also examining online business and developing their e-commerce platforms⁸⁷.

Non-aeronautical revenues of airports have become critically important for airport operators, representing about 40% of airport revenues globally. These revenues can, in some cases, offset the cost base for aeronautical fees and are an integral part of the passenger experience. The extension of non-aeronautical activities depends on the physical space available at the airport, as well as the terminal management philosophy and passenger traffic.

⁸⁶ Global Airport Cities, *What is an Airport City?*, <http://www.globalairportcities.com/airports-and-partners/what-is-an-airport-city>, 31 January 2012

⁸⁷ Jenny Yui Nam Chiang, *Generating Non-Aeronautical Revenue Through E-Commerce: A Comparative Study Of Hong Kong International Airport And London Heathrow Airport*, s.l., The University of Hong Kong, 2019

According to the Airports Council International (ACI) 2021 Airport Economics Report, globally, retail concessions, parking, and property and real estate incomes represent almost two-thirds of non-aeronautical revenues (retail: 26.4%, parking: 20.9%, property and real estate income: 15.2%)⁸⁸.

The two international airports studied in this chapter, selected from diverse geographical areas with different commercial approaches, have pursued a non-aviation business strategy that serves as a model.

Heathrow Airport (LHR) in London, the main "privatized" international airport recognized by Skytrax for years as the best airport in travel retail, and Changi Airport (SIN) in Singapore, as a best practice in terms of luxury retail and, above all, for the unique customer experience provided based on one-of-a-kind services.

In both analyzed cases, it can be observed that airport operators not only ensure the operability of the airport but also seek to derive all possible revenues from their monopoly position. Starting from the core airport business, i.e., air transport, this is used as an economic lever for the development of the commercial area and non-aeronautical sector revenues.

Every airport has its increasingly diversified portfolio of non-aeronautical revenues, always searching for new ways to generate revenues, thereby diversifying risks and mitigating the effects of passenger traffic fluctuations (as seen during economic crises and pandemics).

Airports are developing new commercial and real estate opportunities using lands that are not necessary or suitable for aeronautical purposes. Many are moving toward an "experiential" philosophy to develop authentic customer experiences, linked to a brand or service at the airport, or even cultural events in the area where the airport is located.

⁸⁸ Mark Morris, *How Do Airports Make Money?*, <https://knaviation.net/how-do-airports-make-money/>, 6 October 2022

Since non-aeronautical revenues are historically mainly tied to passenger traffic, previous research has shown that a 1% increase in the global average of passenger satisfaction, as defined by the Airport Service Quality (ASQ) survey, results in an average 1.5% growth in non-aeronautical revenues in broader terms⁸⁹. In other words, creating a smooth and memorable experience for passengers is also associated with a more than proportional increase in revenues and spending propensity.

For example, operators aim to diversify travel retail services to maximize possible obtainable revenues, going so far as to install or allow the installation of all kinds of commercial activities to transform the airport from a "non-place" into an "airport city." These dynamic containers offer commercial, entertainment, social, and cultural services, constituting an economic development engine for the surrounding territory.

Internationally, airports strive to impress passengers and make the airport almost more appealing than the destination⁹⁰.

Moreover, to fully harness the commercial development potential of internal traffic, the range of services offered and the product selection should match the preferences and needs of specific types of passengers. To achieve this goal, airports, along with their retail and F&B (food and beverage) partners, are dedicating increasing resources to understand their customers: analyzing the services offered, the origin and destination of travelers, and conducting complex market research.

These studies aim to determine who and what buys in airport stores, who does not buy and why, the attitudes of potential buyers towards products with a particular quality-price ratio, etc.

⁸⁹ Patrick Lucas, *Non-aeronautical revenues: Diversify and grow*, <https://airport-world.com/non-aeronautical-revenues-diversify-and-grow/>, May 2022

⁹⁰ AVCP - Autorità per la Vigilanza sui Contratti Pubblici di Lavori, Servizi e Forniture, *La gestione aeroportuale*, <https://www.anticorruzione.it/documents/91439/211723/La+Gestione+Aeroportuale.pdf/763996fe-3a5d-a7c5-b414-8f3019d083d1?t=1585298355383>, March 2013

In the following paragraphs, we will delve into the operational strategies of the two airports being compared and highlight the most interesting data for analysis.

The Winning Model of Heathrow Airport in London

Heathrow Airport in London is a benchmark in the world of airport retail, boasting a higher retail revenue per passenger performance compared to major European airports. It is also the main hub in the United Kingdom, making it one of the best examples of an airport built to generate profits. Over the last five years, it has received numerous international awards, earning the title of "Best Airport in Western Europe" and winning the "Best Airport for Shopping" award for 10 consecutive years, along with the "World's Top Airport Terminal" award (2018 and 2019) from the World Airport Awards, all organized by Skytrax⁹¹.

The airport is additionally certified as a **4-Star Airport** by the same entity, covering

“facilities, comfort, cleanliness, shopping, food & beverages, staff service, and security/immigration.”

However, this recognition also highlights certain weaknesses, such as the distance between terminals and the cost of transfers to and from central London:

“T2 and T5 provide the best facility standards, but the terminals are large and can involve considerable walking distances upon arrival and departure. Transferring between terminals is not easy and requires longer transfer times compared to many global hub airports. Transportation links to central London can be expensive using taxis or the express train.”

Owned and managed by Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited, a consortium comprising various private investors and investment companies, including the multinational Spanish company Ferrovial SA (25%), Qatar Investment Authority (20%), and Caisse de dépôt et placement du Québec (12.62%)⁹², Heathrow Airport is a civil airport. The company is subject to financial

⁹¹ Skytrax, <https://skytraxratings.com/>

⁹² Heathrow Airport, <https://www.heathrow.com/company/about-heathrow>

regulation by both the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA), *responsible for the regulation of aviation safety in the UK*⁹³, and the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA), *a non-ministerial department promoting competitive markets and assisting individuals, businesses, and the UK economy*⁹⁴.

Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited is responsible for the supervision and administration of the airport, while hundreds of other companies operate within the airport. Essentially, this is a privately-owned airport in which the UK government does not hold any stake.

Furthermore, Heathrow Airport actively contributes to achieving the United Nations' sustainable development goals by 2030. It has already made significant strides towards growing the airport sustainably⁹⁵, such as progress in decarbonizing airport infrastructure as of January 2020 and efforts to manage airport infrastructure with zero carbon emissions by the mid-2030s. These initiatives are part of the guidelines toward sustainability. For example, the voluntary pursuit of these policies in recent years has significantly reduced the revenues from Heathrow's parking compared to other major airports or airport groups in Europe, replacing this with incentivizing the use of public transportation like the subway or train.

⁹³ Civil Aviation Authority, <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/civil-aviation-authority>

⁹⁴ Competition and Markets Authority, <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/competition-and-markets-authority>

⁹⁵ Heathrow Airport, *Financial results for the full year ended 31 December 2019*, https://www.heathrow.com/content/dam/heathrow/web/common/documents/company/investor/reports-and-presentations/financial-results/2019/Heathrow_Limited_Q4_2019_results_release.pdf

The airport officially transitioned from military to civilian in 1946. Terminal 1 opened in 1969 when 5 million passengers passed through the airport annually, but it was later closed in 2015. Approximately a decade after that closure, Heathrow saw 27 million passengers per year, necessitating the opening of the new Terminal 4, which occurred in 1986. In the new millennium, with the increase in passenger traffic, Terminal 5 was opened in 2008, followed by the new Terminal 2, also known as "The Queen," in 2014⁹⁶.

Specifically, Terminal 2 was developed through significant collaboration with the primary retail provider, World Duty Free Group, during the design phase. Although the shops are spread across two floors, passengers immediately have a full view of the retail space, allowing for orientation and the opportunity to plan their dwell time to visit the stores. The layout design of Terminal 2 also ensures easy access for all passengers to the central duty-free area, with "walk-by" access to all other shops. This innovative layout was designed to strike a balance between maximizing shop exposure to passengers and providing adequate space for seating, orientation, and efficiently managing passenger flow to various boarding gates. The airport's goal is to concentrate both passengers' dwell time and shopping interest in the same area, thus maximizing the shopping opportunity and interest while avoiding dispersion of potential customers. This integrated approach to terminal design, combining physical infrastructure and retail shopping, has allowed the airport to create an environment within the terminal that supports both retail activity and overall passenger satisfaction with the airport⁹⁷.

The airport serves over 190 destinations in 82 countries with direct flights through approximately 80 airlines, providing employment for more than 76,000 employees in total⁹⁸.

⁹⁶ Heathrow Airport, <https://www.heathrow.com/company/about-heathrow>

⁹⁷ Harry Bush, Daniel Storey, *Economic impact of duty free and travel retail in Europe, a report for the Duty Free World Council*, <https://www.readkong.com/page/economic-impact-of-duty-free-and-travel-retail-in-europe-2745770>, March 2016

⁹⁸ Caroline Louring-Andersen, Nina Scheler Vindel, *Expanding Capacity At Heathrow Airport. Designing A Campaign From A Stakeholder Perspective*, s.l., Copenhagen Business School, 2017

According to estimates by Wendover Productions⁹⁹, managing Heathrow costs about \$1,485,650,000 per year. This cost includes the salaries of approximately 6,500 direct company employees (actually a small part of the total mentioned, approximately 76,000 people working at Heathrow for the hundreds of companies within).

To support these costs of about one and a half billion dollars in expenses each year, it is crucial to analyze the average earnings per passenger. For instance, in the calendar year 2015, Heathrow earned £8.55 per passenger from its commercial revenue streams, reaching the highest level of commercial revenue per passenger among major UK airports (+£1 per passenger of Manchester and +£2.3 per passenger of Gatwick)¹⁰⁰. Moreover, it ranked first globally for commercial revenues per passenger among major competing airports (this revenue per passenger share increased in the subsequent years, consistently keeping Heathrow at the top globally for commercial revenues).

⁹⁹ Wendover Productions, *How Airports Make Money*, <https://www.youtube.com/@Wendoverproductions>, 17 July 2018

¹⁰⁰ Steer Davies Gleave, *Heathrow Airport - Review of Commercial Revenues*, Final Report for Civil Aviation Authority, https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/docs/33/1563b_H7_Commercial_Revenues_report_by_SDG.pdf, April 2017

Source: Steer Davies Gleave analysis of published airport annual accounts

Heathrow's retail activities generated gross revenue of £439 million in 2015, with 30% coming from the Duty & Tax-Free category (£128 million). According to Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited (2018), the primary source of non-aviation revenue for the airport includes retail, airport property rental, baggage management, passenger check-in, Heathrow Express fees, parking, and VIP lounge/products.

During the period 2013-2016, the annual growth in traffic averaged around +1.5%. For nine consecutive years until the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic, Heathrow experienced positive growth with a healthy financial performance, accommodating a record 80.9 million passengers in 2019 (+1% compared to 2018). About 82% of passengers rated the airport as "Excellent" or "Very Good" following improvement efforts through a private investment of over £12 billion.

The revenues for the airport increased by 3.4% compared to the previous year, driven by the increased demand for flights (which grew by nearly 25% over the last ten years), supporting an

additional £856 million investment in the airport in 2019 alone¹⁰¹. All of this significantly improved the customer service experience.

In the retail sector, revenues in the calendar year 2018 saw a 7.7% increase, reaching £659 million, accounting for approximately 23% of total revenues. When considering only "retail concessions," there was a 10.5% annual increase (Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited, 2018).

The impact of Brexit should not be underestimated. Any medium to long-term economic projections for Heathrow remain uncertain, given the weakening of the pound. However, it may attract non-EU travelers to purchase goods at the airport, benefiting from lower costs and duty-free privileges. Simultaneously, Brexit could pose a threat to the airport, as 35% of the incoming and outgoing air traffic at Heathrow is from EU countries (Heathrow Airport Limited, 2018).

As one of the world's largest airport hubs, Heathrow serves a wide range of global markets. Over the last ten years, there has been a strong growth in international traffic (from 61 million in 2005 to almost 71 million in 2016), primarily towards Latin America and the Middle East, coinciding with a reduction in passenger numbers for domestic routes¹⁰².

In terms of passenger profiling, in recent years, UK citizens have constituted 36-37% of the passenger mix, with other significant groups including citizens of the EU and EFTA countries (2015: 25%), North America (2015: approximately 18%), and East Asia/Australia (2015: approximately 8%). The mix of passenger nationalities is not uniform across Heathrow's terminals and varies in a dynamic context of airline transfers from one terminal to another for operational reasons. These movements can also involve shifting groups with high or low

¹⁰¹ Heathrow Airport, *Financial results for the full year ended 31 December 2019*, [https://www.heathrow.com/content/dam/heathrow/web/common/documents/company/investor/reports-and-presentations/financial-results/2019/Heathrow Limited Q4 2019 results release.pdf](https://www.heathrow.com/content/dam/heathrow/web/common/documents/company/investor/reports-and-presentations/financial-results/2019/Heathrow%20Limited%20Q4%202019%20results%20release.pdf)

¹⁰² Steer Davies Gleave, *Heathrow Airport - Review of Commercial Revenues*, Final Report for Civil Aviation Authority, [https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/docs/33/1563b_H7 Commercial Revenues report by SDG.pdf](https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/docs/33/1563b_H7_Commercial_Revenues_report_by_SDG.pdf), April 2017

spending intentions, creating an effect that can potentially be advantageous or detrimental to retail sector revenues, depending on the passenger groups and terminals involved.

Structurally, Heathrow has reached its maximum operational capacity based on its architecture, with a maximum of approximately 1,300 flights per day¹⁰³. To increase revenues without impacting the budget for constructing additional space, it would be necessary to increase the percentage of larger aircraft. This is one of the reasons why it's striking that the airport is much better connected with extra-UK flights compared to domestic flights (8 destinations, the same as it has for China alone, for example¹⁰⁴).

But in detail, where do Heathrow's non-aviation revenues come from? Primarily through passenger services, including retail areas, food & beverage, currency exchange offices, advertising spaces, rental cars, and parking. Except for parking, these services operate under a "concession¹⁰⁵" where a third party is responsible for the service, and the airport receives a concession fee based on a percentage of the concessionaire's net turnover. Car parking, on the other hand, operates under a management contract where Heathrow collects all revenues, and the parking operator is compensated, plus operating costs, for providing parking services to passengers.

In addition, Heathrow earns through retail by receiving a portion of each sale. In 2018/19, on average, restaurants inside the airport earned \$0.95/passenger, retail shops around \$5.15/passenger, parking added another \$2.03/passenger, other minor sources (rental cars and

¹⁰³ Alessio Caprodossi, *Il nuovo volto dell'aeroporto londinese di Heathrow*, <https://www.wired.it/lifestyle/design/2019/06/19/aeroporto-heathrow-piano-espansione/>, 19 June 2019

¹⁰⁴ Wendover Productions, *How Airports Make Money*, <https://www.youtube.com/@Wendoverproductions>, 17 July 2018

¹⁰⁵ A concession is a public-private partnership (PPP) in which a public authority (Concession Authority) grants specific long-term rights to a private or semi-public organization (Concessionaire). The respective roles are clearly defined between the private investor who finances, builds, maintains, and operates the infrastructure, and the public authority that determines the program, selects the concessionaire company, ensures that the work is carried out satisfactorily, and monitors the quality of the infrastructure's operation.

The contract defines the transfer of risk between the public entity and the concessionaire company.

VIP lounges, for example) added another \$3.04/passenger. Additionally, the Express train to central London contributed another \$2.15/passenger, totaling about \$13.32/passenger. On average, the airport adds revenue of approximately \$29/ticket per passenger (including airline-related services, paid directly to the airport, such as landing fees, time on the runway, check-in, gate space, and many other services)¹⁰⁶. This represents one of the highest retail revenues per passenger of any airport in the world (for instance, Washington Dulles Airport earns approximately \$5.68/passenger).

In the calendar year 2015, Heathrow's management company showed a net sales gain of £641 million¹⁰⁷, distributed as follows:

Source: HAL regulatory accounts 2015

This highlights how 50% of Heathrow's commercial revenues in 2015 came from retail (split between duty & tax-free, airside shops, and other retail sales). It demonstrates the significant weight the non-aviation sector has in maintaining and profiting the airport.

¹⁰⁶ Wendover Productions, *How Airports Make Money*, <https://www.youtube.com/@Wendoverproductions>, 17 July 2018

¹⁰⁷ Steer Davies Gleave, *Heathrow Airport - Review of Commercial Revenues*, Final Report for Civil Aviation Authority, https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/docs/33/1563b_H7_Commercial_Revenues_report_by_SDG.pdf, April 2017

Generally, most airports experience a radical shift in their revenue streams due to the expansion of their commercial spaces. London Heathrow Airport, particularly with its Terminal 5 resembling a luxury shopping mall rather than a conventional terminal, stands as the most advanced example in utilizing data for optimizing the shopping experience. Sales assistants fluent in Arabic are scheduled during flights departing for Dubai, and detailed guidance is provided on how and where to place merchandise in stores to encourage sales based on specific behavioral and physical characteristics of passing customers. With a dedicated personal shopper service for its 2,000 monthly first and business class travelers, the London airport saw a 7.7% revenue increase, totaling £612 million in 2016 in the retail sector alone¹⁰⁸.

Notably, Terminal 5 has been voted the world's best airport terminal six times since its opening in 2008 (Skytrax World Airport Awards), offering a pleasant airport experience with trendy shops, restaurants, and luxury lounges.

Furthermore, Heathrow has developed its own online retail platform: the e-commerce platform, "Heathrow Boutique," was launched in early 2018. Through Heathrow Boutique, the "Reserve & Collect" service is available to all passengers: products can be pre-booked at Heathrow Boutique from 3 days to 24 hours before the flight.

Heathrow also employs various commercial strategies to increase passenger spending, typical of airports. For example, in Terminal 3, from security checks to the gate, all passengers must follow a mandatory path through duty-free, significantly boosting retail sales. The pedestrian paths in duty-free always veer left, allowing more space for shopping on the right side of the path. According to the consulting firm Intervistas¹⁰⁹, this leads to higher revenues as most people are right-handed and will spend more time looking to the right.

¹⁰⁸ Ilaria Caielli, *Perché i negozi dentro gli aeroporti vendono più degli altri*, <https://www.wired.it/economia/business/2017/07/13/negozi-dentro-gli-aeroporti/>, 13 July 2017

¹⁰⁹ Steve Cameron, *Sneaky Ways Airports Get You To Spend Money*, <https://www.businessinsider.com/airports-spend-more-money-duty-free-shopping-restaurants-2019-8?r=US&IR=T>, 2019

Additionally, the airport does not display the departure gate for flights until approximately 25-90 minutes before departure¹¹⁰, allowing passengers a longer dwell time in the airside area filled with shops, restaurants, souvenir shops, and last-minute food and beverage options like drinks, water, or snacks (this strategy is primarily used in European airports but not elsewhere).

The strategic worldwide positioning in terms of connections is also not to be underestimated, a result of managerial choices by the Heathrow Airport management company. Heathrow is one of the few airports in the world with non-stop service to all continents, maintaining the advantage of being an airport focused on long-haul service, which, according to industry reports, transports primarily higher-spending passengers.

This connects to Heathrow's strategic advantage in managing dwell time: while the international average arrival time at the airport is about 2 hours and 17 minutes before the flight, at Heathrow, passengers arrive on average 2 hours and 51 minutes before. This translates to more dwell time for shopping in the airside area¹¹¹.

¹¹⁰ Steve Cameron, *Sneaky Ways Airports Get You To Spend Money*, <https://www.businessinsider.com/airports-spend-more-money-duty-free-shopping-restaurants-2019-8?r=US&IR=T>, 2019

¹¹¹ Wendover Productions, *How Airports Make Money*, <https://www.youtube.com/@Wendoverproductions>, 17 July 2018

Changi Airport and the "shopping experience" concept

According to the Tax Free World Association (TFWA), the global association for duty-free and travel retail, Asia accounted for 40% of the entire airport travel retail turnover in the early years of the new millennium, with a 12% growth between 2012 and 2013. In this ranking, seven airports in the top ten worldwide are in the Asia-Pacific region, and among them, Changi Airport was already in the third position¹¹².

Changi Airport is one of Singapore's main airports and is known to be one of the best in the world for its efficiency and the quality of services offered. It is also famous for its luxury commercial area that has been developed in recent years. It has been awarded multiple times as the "**World's Best Airport**" by the World Airport Awards organized by Skytrax¹¹³, and it is certified by the same entity as a 5-Star Airport:

"Singapore Changi Airport is a major transit airport, delivering a very high and consistent quality level across the extensive facilities and staff service. The opening of Jewel Changi Airport, a multi-dimensional destination filled with inspiring attractions, unique retail, and dining concepts, has enabled Changi Airport to create a unique airport facility."

This recognition is based on various categories, including operational efficiency, passenger services, airport experience, and innovation, as well as attention to sustainability, with measures taken to reduce environmental impact such as the use of recycled materials, energy-saving lighting, and the promotion of eco-friendly products. It is a civil/military airport managed by the Changi Airport Group under the purview of the Ministry of Finance of the Singapore government.

¹¹² Alessandro Marchetto, Matteo Panatta, *Aeroporti: il retail passa da qui*, in *Travel Retail Italia, rivista di Studi e Analisi*, Rubbettino, May - August 2016

¹¹³ Skytrax, <https://skytraxratings.com/>

Its history dates back to the early 1970s when the Singaporean government first decided to upgrade the existing Paya Lebar Airport. However, due to the exponential growth in passenger numbers beyond its capacity, they opted to construct a new airport instead.

The construction of Changi Airport commenced in 1975 on marshy land in the east of Singapore. The ambitious project required land reclamation and leveling to create the base for airport development. The Singaporean authorities made a significant investment in its construction, officially inaugurating the airport in 1981, with the aim of transforming it into a major transportation hub in the region. They envisioned it as a hub of travel not only physically but also in terms of shopping experiences, being the first to introduce airport gardens and free phone calls for transit passengers¹¹⁴.

Given the enormous number of transit passengers, surpassing 10 million in 1986, construction began for the opening of Terminal 2 (completed in 1991), the establishment of the first rooftop swimming pool in an airport in 1995, and a range of other services for transit passengers (cinema

¹¹⁴ Changi Airport Group, *A History of Firsts*, <https://www.changiairport.com/corporate/about-us/our-story.html#anchorHF>

and a sports arena) towards the late 1990s. Today, Terminal 2, the busiest one, hosts over 70 retail outlets and more than 25 F&B points¹¹⁵.

Terminals 3 ("*eco-friendly green terminal*") and 4 were completed in 2008 and 2017, respectively, bringing the airport to a total capacity of about 82 million passengers per year¹¹⁶ and a total of 382,000 flights in 2019¹¹⁷. In the landside area, Terminal 3 boasts avant-garde design and is recognized as a full-fledged shopping mall, featuring multidimensional shopping and the highest number of retail, services, and dining spaces. Terminal 4, on the other hand, is characterized by 17,000 m² of shops and restaurants, with ample spaces filled with natural light and trees along the entire shopping path.

In addition to the airport's main structure, a luxury terminal called the "JetQuay CIP Terminal" was added, open to all passengers of all airlines, with an entrance fee, inaugurated in 2006. It offers *top-notch VIP services including faster check-in and immigration clearance, a dining area, and a limousine service to accompany passengers to and from the boarding area*¹¹⁸.

A recent study commissioned to Airport Dimensions has shown how airports need to adapt their retail offerings and the experience concept to attract the modern traveler and increase revenue. The research data revealed that today's passengers are open to new experiences while at the airport: for instance, almost two-thirds (64%) stated an appeal to health and wellness services, 61% would like to see more body care facilities, and over half (56%) would want the

¹¹⁵ Changi Airport Group, www.changiairport.com

¹¹⁶ Jenny Reid, *The big picture: 40 years of Singapore Changi*, <https://www.busesstraveller.com/business-travel/2019/07/17/the-big-picture-40-years-of-singapore-changi/>, 17 July 2019

¹¹⁷ Nicholas Yong, *Changi Airport: Hanging out at the world's best airport*, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-65171824>, 12 April 2023

¹¹⁸ JetQuay, https://www.jetquay.com.sg/who_we_are.php

option of exclusive paid lounges during their journey¹¹⁹. It's within this realm that Changi Airport has moved over the past decades: the traveler's experience.

Changi Airport is renowned for its unique attractions and services, such as the Butterfly Garden, Sunflower Garden, outdoor swimming pool, cinemas, wellness centers, and exclusive lounges for passengers. Outside Terminal 4, there's even a life-sized dinosaur *exhibition* for a mile.

The year 2019 marked another strategic year with the opening of Jewel Changi, an area of the Terminal designed by architect Moshe Safdie (Marina Bay Sands Hotel) and with a cost of 1.3 billion dollars as a joint venture between airport operator Changi Airport Group (CAG) and real estate developer CapitaLand. The area features over 280 shops and dining spots, a five-story garden with 2,500 trees and 100,000 shrubs, along with two pedestrian walkways, and the famous 40m Rain Vortex, the world's tallest indoor waterfall¹²⁰, a 130-room luxury hotel, an 11-screen cinema, and the world's only airport-based Apple Store.

¹¹⁹ Airport World - The Magazine of Airports Council International, *Airport travellers open to new retail experiences*, <https://airport-world.com/airport-travellers-open-to-new-retail-experiences-new-research/>, 28 December 2022

¹²⁰ Karamjit Kaur, *Jewel Changi Airport to open on April 17 with 280 shops and F&B outlets; public preview from April 11 to 16*, <https://www.straitstimes.com/singapore/transport/jewel-changi-airport-to-open-on-april-17>, 7 March 2019

Jewel Changi aims to position Changi Airport as a "brand" tourist destination, akin to the concepts of Dubai's Burj Khalifa or Paris's Louvre. Within six months of its opening in April 2019, Jewel Changi had already welcomed 50 million visitors¹²¹. The success of Jewel Changi mirrors Singapore's ability to consistently provide cutting-edge mega-projects that combine economic development, environmental sustainability, and enhanced quality of life. Factors contributing to this capacity include:

- Ongoing infrastructural investments by the Singaporean Government.
- A commitment to investing in public sector planning and engineering expertise.
- Singapore's practice of constantly engaging with competitors large and small to seek any advantage.
- A balanced approach to privatization that encourages innovation and entrepreneurship.

¹²¹ Nicholas Yong, *Changi Airport: Hanging out at the world's best airport*, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-65171824>, 12 April 2023

- Top-down government commitment to ensuring that major infrastructural investments serve both the residents' quality of life and national economic development¹²².

These projects within Changi Airport have been developed over the decades to meet, among other things, the opportunities of the non-aviation business sector, a sector in continuous growth, and a modern concept of the "shopping experience". Scientific research in the sector has shown that the terminal layout and hence the physical characteristics of the environment help create a positive emotional state, thus actively influencing the traveler's spending decisions. It's no coincidence that the airport even has its fragrance: a custom fragrance with floral and spice notes diffused throughout Changi¹²³.

Shopping and dining are integral to the entire "airport experience" at Changi, parallel to the landside phase (check-in, immigration passport control). In addition to contributing to the overall Changi experience, non-aviation revenues from travel retail help maintain competitive airport fees for airlines, strengthening Changi's position as a leading global airport hub.

In terms of connectivity and route network, Changi Airport is currently served by over 80 airlines flying to approximately 130 cities worldwide. North America, South Asia, and Oceania have witnessed the strongest recovery in passenger traffic¹²⁴.

Furthermore, there's a category called "*Best Airport Leisure Amenities*" within the international World Airport Awards, won by Singapore's airport in 2023. This reflects the amenities Changi offers, including pools on green rooftops, yoga and meditation rooms, 4D cinemas, golf courses, and a 12-meter slide.

Changi Airport ranks among the top three airports globally for concession sales. In 2015-2016, concession sales totaled 1.6 billion, surpassing the growth in air traffic. There are over 76,000

¹²² John Landis, *Singapore's Jewel Changi Airport - always raising the bar*, in *Megaprojects for Megacities*, s.l., Edward Elgar, 2022

¹²³ Nicholas Yong, *Changi Airport: Hanging out at the world's best airport*, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-65171824>, 12 April 2023

¹²⁴ Joe Bates, *The Changi way*, <https://airport-world.com/the-changi-way/>, 30 December 2022

square meters of concession spaces rented by 360 retail outlets and services and 140 restaurants scattered across the four terminals¹²⁵.

Notably, according to a 2019 analysis by Cheng-Lung Wu & Yimeng Chen on non-aviation sector revenues of various airports, Changi achieved 52% of its total revenue from this sector, compared to 35% for Frankfurt International and 33% for Los Angeles¹²⁶.

"Changi is no mere travel hub: it is an almost iconic hangout spot, beloved by Singaporeans¹²⁷". The airport is known for a unique approach to a "shopping experience" associated with luxury retail. Hence, alongside the main attractions of the airport, a luxury shopping experience is offered with a vast selection of high-end brands. It's about creating a world-class shopping environment that goes beyond just purchasing luxury products. Commercial spaces are designed with great attention to aesthetics and customer experience, aiming to offer an elegant and refined environment while creating a "special experience". Exclusive products and limited editions, often created specifically for Changi Airport and not available elsewhere, are showcased.

High-fashion boutiques, luxury jewelers, branded watch stores, luxury cosmetics shops (Louis Vuitton, Chanel, Gucci, Hermès, Prada, Cartier, Rolex, Tiffany & Co., Bulgari, Dior, Salvatore Ferragamo, Burberry, Omega, Montblanc, Swarovski, Miu Miu, Jimmy Choo, and many others) are interspersed with exclusive lounges, luxury spas, gourmet restaurants, and personal shopping services available for passengers seeking a first-class treatment during their airport stay.

¹²⁵ Joan C. Henderson, *Airport roles: Pushing the boundaries at Singapore's Changi Airport*, in *Asian Journal of Tourism Research*, 2017

¹²⁶ Cheng-Lung Wu, Chen Yimeng, *Effects of passenger characteristics and terminal layout on airport retail revenue: an agent-based simulation approach*, in *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 2019

¹²⁷ Nicholas Yong, *Changi Airport: Hanging out at the world's best airport*, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-65171824>, 12 April 2023

Singapore's airport also offers, in collaboration with brands, certain product customization services such as engraving initials on high-end liquor bottles, watches, and luxury bags¹²⁸.

One of the travel retail strategies employed by the airport is maintaining an attractive mix of brands and introducing new concepts to cater to ever-evolving consumer trends and expectations. Over the years, numerous new retail concepts have been launched, raising the bar for in-store experiences. These include the world's first duplex stores for cosmetics, perfumes, wines, and spirits, the introduction of globally exclusive products through the Changi First program, 24-hour online shopping through the *iShopChangi portal*¹²⁹, and more.

¹²⁸ Marta Casadei, *Shopping in aeroporto: Singapore e Zurigo i migliori, in Italia spicca Fiumicino*, https://www.ilsole24ore.com/art/shopping-aeroporto-singapore-e-zurigo-migliori-italia-spicca-venezia-ABhwCiaB?refresh_ce=1, 5 March 2019

¹²⁹ *iShopChangi* (www.ishopchangi.com) is the e-commerce platform of Changi Airport, catering to both transit and non-transit travelers. It offers over 14,000 products from approximately 500 brands, ranging from clothing to electronics, wines to cosmetics, and household items, all linked to duty-free offerings. Passengers can shop online from 30 days prior to departure up to 18 hours before their flight, and then pick up their purchases at one of the airport's 4 terminals or have them delivered to an address in Singapore.

Additionally, exclusive "Changi First" products can be purchased before they are introduced at the airport. The e-commerce platform, established in 2013, has received several international awards over the years, including "Best Website – Retail Customer Facing".

In the airport's public areas, Changi is also introducing new food and beverage concepts such as new-to-Singapore brands, themed restaurants, and multi-concept food kiosks to cater to various preferences. Additionally, similar to many other major hub airports, Changi has passengers who spend a significant amount of time in the airside area. Hence, a bus tour service of Singapore has been developed for those in transit for more than five hours.

Another success factor is promoting shopping throughout the airport through the "*Be a Changi Millionaire*" campaign. To participate, passengers and airport visitors had to shop or dine at Changi Airport and spend a minimum of 50 Singapore dollars on a single receipt¹³⁰. The campaign proved to be a significant awareness factor for Changi Airport's shopping and dining offerings, making it a rewarding place for shopping and dining. Since its launch in 2010, the main campaign has attracted millions of shoppers, crowned nine millionaires, and two car winners¹³¹.

Even free experiences "*to kill the time*" before the flight help build excitement, which industry studies consider favorable to purchasing propensity. Massages, 11-screen cinemas, the Butterfly Garden, the 4-story and 22,000 square meter Forest Valley with orchid gardens, sunflowers, cacti, a snooze lounge, the 14,000 square meter Canopy Park with mazes, pedestrian paths, slides, and a playground for children, and the aforementioned Rain Vortex Waterfall, the airport's main attraction, are some of these additional elements.

These additions contribute to creating the so-called "*shopping experience*", a unique experience for passengers, encouraging them to spend more time in luxury shopping inside the airport. An amazing travel retail experience not only enhances a passenger's overall airport experience but also gives Changi a greater competitive edge as an airport hub.

¹³⁰ Changi Airport Group, *The real role of retail at Changi*, <https://www.changiairport.com/corporate/media-centre/changijourneys/the-changi-experience/the-real-role-of-retail-in-changi.html>, March 2019

¹³¹ Dermot Davitt, *High-profile promotion: 'Be a Changi Millionaire' campaign draws 1.4 million entries*, <https://www.moodiedavittreport.com/high-profile-promotion-be-a-changi-millionaire-campaign-draws-1-4-million-entries/>, 25 January 2019

In terms of numbers, Singapore Changi Airport handled 68.3 million passengers in 2019, exceeding 2.8 billion dollars in sales for the same year¹³².

Changi's strength lies in deliberately presenting itself not only as a destination, departure, or stopover in a journey, but also primarily as a destination for tourism, leisure, shopping, and dining: not just a simple travel hub, but an almost iconic gathering place, beloved by Singaporeans. It's easy to find locals shopping for groceries, shopping, or simply sitting in front of the fountain to enjoy the experience.

Of course, all this was made possible through the political/strategic choices made over the decades: the airport is easily accessible via the metro and bus, so it's not uncommon to find locals spending the entire day at Changi as they would at any mall or hangout spot. You can watch a movie at the cinema, eat, buy groceries, even find a quiet place to read or study, besides it has also become a destination for wedding photography services and reunion dinners¹³³.

After the crisis due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which had halted the positive trend of revenues, the travel retail sector at Changi Airport has seen continuous and steady growth in the early months of 2023, with overall sales increasing compared to the previous year. In January, sales reached almost 60% of 2019 levels, reaching 823.4 million dollars in sales recorded last year after Singapore lifted border restrictions in April¹³⁴.

In conclusion, the airport itself is a tourist attraction: the uses of the entire infrastructure, from airport development to tourist events, reinforce the concept of it being a **destination** by connecting it with the authenticity and originality of local resources, going beyond simple aeronautical activities. Therefore, the audience it caters to isn't limited to airlines and passengers;

¹³² Andrew Pentol, *EXCLUSIVE: Changi exceeds S\$2.8bn sales in 2019*, <https://www.trbusiness.com/regional-news/asia-pacific/exclusive-changi-exceeds-s2-8bn-sales-in-2019/192771>, 23 July 2020

¹³³ Nicholas Yong, *Changi Airport: Hanging out at the world's best airport*, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-65171824>, 12 April 2023

¹³⁴ Irene Dong, *Changi Airport retail sales continue to rise as travel rebounds*, <https://insideretail.asia/2023/05/10/changi-airport-retail-sales-continue-to-rise-as-travel-rebounds/>, 10 May 2023

other users, such as residents or tourists, spend time visiting the airport as well, and it is these airport users who have the potential to increase non-aeronautical revenues¹³⁵.

¹³⁵ Thanavutd Chutipongdech, Rugphong Vongsaraj, *The Success behind the World's Best Airport: The Rise of the Changi*, s.l., Chulalongkorn University, 2021

Comparison of Business Models

This paragraph aims to analyze the financials of previously discussed airport business models, namely Changi Airport in Singapore, recognized as an example of a "shopping experience," and Heathrow Airport in London, the most famous case of an international private airport.

As highlighted in the specific paragraphs, it emerges that Heathrow Airport's non-aviation business model is more "practical," aimed at achieving revenues through cutting-edge strategies in marketing and passenger profiling, while Changi, on the other hand, creates a true "*airport experience*" that indirectly generates commercial revenues.

Regarding financials, due to different reporting periods driven by varying accounting principles, a comparison can be made primarily based on differences from the previous administrative year. I have chosen the pre-Covid period for analysis to study the situation during a phase of exponential growth in the non-aviation business sector not yet impacted by the pandemic. For this reason, the administrative year for Changi spans from April 1, 2018, to March 31, 2019, while for Heathrow, it covers January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2019.

From a financial standpoint, **Changi Airport Group (Singapore) Pte Ltd** (hereinafter, CAG) was established on June 16, 2009, and on July 1, 2009, the corporatization of Singapore Changi Airport followed. As a company managing Changi Airport, CAG undertakes key functions focusing on airport operations and management, airport hub development, commercial activities, and airport emergency services¹³⁶.

In the fiscal year 2018/19, there was a 5.2% growth in passenger traffic, leading Changi Airport to handle a record 66.3 million passengers—almost +80% compared to the 36.9 million passengers managed a decade earlier, at the beginning of corporatization. On the commercial front, concession sales grew by 8.1%, reaching a record level of S\$ 2.8 billion. The connectivity with China continued to improve during the fiscal year 2018/19, with an additional three urban

¹³⁶ Changi Airport Group, *Annual Report*, <http://www.changiairport.com/content/dam/cacorp/publications/Annual%20Reports/2019/CAG-AR2019-Corporate-Information.pdf>, 2019

links bringing the total to 37. Chinese traffic increased by 7.9%, while traffic with India, another significant market, grew by 10.5%. Together, these two markets represented 17.8% of Changi's total passenger traffic growth during the year 2018/19. Analyzing the publicly available financial statement on Changi Airport's website for the fiscal year 2018/19 (pre-pandemic), the Group reported a consolidated operating revenue of S\$ 3 billion, (+16.8% compared to 2017/18, which had a consolidated operating revenue of S\$ 2.6 billion).

Financial Review

Financial Highlights					
	FY14/15	FY15/16	FY16/17	FY17/18	FY18/19
Profit & Loss (S\$'ml)					
Total revenue	2,150	2,164	2,305	2,602	3,040
Total expenses	1,255	1,284	1,401	1,649	2,120
EBITDA	1,171	1,167	1,208	1,310	1,466
Profit after tax	782	784	657	835	574
Profit attributable to equity holder of the Company	784	786	662	849	677
Financial Position (S\$'ml)					
Assets	7,564	8,460	9,260	14,894	15,108
Liabilities	1,441	1,874	2,223	6,457	6,647
Equity	6,123	6,586	7,037	8,437	8,461
Equity attributable to equity holder of the Company	6,127	6,594	7,044	7,600	7,839
Financial Ratios					
EBITDA margin	54.5%	53.9%	52.4%	50.3%	48.2%
NPAT margin	36.4%	36.2%	28.5%	32.1%	18.9%
Return on equity	13.2%	12.3%	9.6%	11.6%	8.8%

Source: Changi Airport FY 2018/19 - Corporate Information

The operating revenues of Changi Airport increased by 8.1% (S\$ 2.6 billion), driven by the significant growth in passenger numbers and higher revenues from airport concessions. These, along with rental revenues, continued to grow strongly at +5.9% (S\$ 1.3 billion) compared to the previous fiscal year. Concession sales by tenants grew by 8.1% annually, reaching a record

of over S\$ 2.8 billion, aided by intensive marketing activities and promotions for Changi Airport, as well as ongoing updates and renewal of commercial spaces that boosted sales.

On the cost side, total expenses increased partly due to high operating costs associated with the opening of new facilities like Terminal 4. Essentially, the robust performance of the non-aviation segment allowed CAG to fund and maintain competitive aeronautical charges at Changi Airport. Overall, the Group achieved an Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization (EBITDA¹³⁷) of nearly S\$ 1.5 billion in the 2018/19 fiscal year, showing an 11.9% improvement compared to the previous year (S\$ 1.3 billion in the 2017/18 fiscal year). The net profit, or net earnings attributable to shareholders, was lower by 20.3% at S\$ 677 million, mainly due to losses from other core activities of the Group. The net equity increased by 3.1%, reaching S\$ 7.8 billion, providing a solid equity base of S\$ 15.1 billion in the 2018/19 fiscal year, compared to approximately S\$ 14.9 billion in the previous fiscal year¹³⁸. This strength facilitated investments for the maintenance and enhancement of airport facilities, along with significant development projects, such as S\$ 1.5 billion for the maintenance and expansion of Terminal 1.

Regarding Heathrow Airport, as mentioned earlier, it's essential to note the different reporting periods for financial statements compared to Changi Airport, owing to different accounting principles. In this case, the UK model follows a fiscal year that coincides with the calendar year (January 1 - December 31). Similarly, for Heathrow Airport, the last financial statement before the pandemic outbreak was considered following the rationale applied for Changi Airport.

It should be specified that Heathrow Airport is subject to economic regulation by the Civil Aviation Authority (CAA), an independent aviation regulatory authority in the UK responsible

¹³⁷ EBITDA, also known as Gross Operating Margin, is the acronym for "Earnings Before Interest Tax Depreciation Amortization," meaning profit before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization. It is a profitability indicator that, compared to net income, keeps certain types of costs separate. More importantly, it is a key measure used to evaluate cash flows of businesses and the overall financial health of accounts.

¹³⁸ All data was taken from the "Financial Statements 2018/2019, Corporate Information" of Changi Airport, at the following link:

http://www.changiairport.com/content/dam/cacorp/publications/Annual%20Reports/2019/CAG-AR18_19-Full-Web-Financial.pdf

for economic regulation, airspace policy, safety, and consumer protection. Heathrow operates under a license granted by the CAA in February 2014, which includes a cap on Heathrow's airport charges. Economic regulation is designed to enable regulated airports in the UK to generate sufficient revenue to fund their operational and capital expenditure needs and provide a regulated return on their Regulatory Asset Base (RAB)¹³⁹.

Heathrow Airport Limited¹⁴⁰ is an indirectly controlled company of Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited; financial activities align with Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited and the broader Heathrow Airport Holdings Limited Group (the "**HAHL Group**"), as well as Heathrow (SP) Limited Group. The board of directors of HAML determines the group's long-term strategy, ensuring ethical conduct, adequate resources to achieve its goals, monitoring performance, and meeting responsibilities as a significant airport group. The HAML Group is owned by a consortium of investors (the "Shareholders"), details of which are reported in the table below as of December 31, 2019.

¹³⁹ "RAB" stands for "Regulatory Asset Base," referring to the value of assets of a regulated company or a company in the public utility sector. This value is used as the basis for calculating approved tariffs and yields.

The concept of RAB is particularly relevant in public utility sectors that are subject to government regulation, such as energy, water, gas, and transportation infrastructure. Regulation is designed to ensure a balance between providing essential services to society and protecting consumers' interests.

¹⁴⁰ Heathrow Airport Limited is a private limited company incorporated in the United Kingdom and registered in England and Wales.

The registered office is The Compass Centre, Nelson Road, Hounslow, Middlesex, TW6 2GW. The parent company of the Company is Heathrow (AH) Limited. The ultimate parent of Heathrow (AH) Limited is Heathrow SP Limited, for which the consolidated financial statements are prepared. The ultimate controlling entity for which the consolidated financial statements are prepared is FG Topco Limited.

Shareholder	% held
Ferrovial Hubco Netherlands B.V. (an indirect subsidiary of Ferrovial, S.A., Spain)	25.00%
Qatar Holding LLC Qatar Holding Aviation (a wholly-owned subsidiary of Qatar Holding LLC)	20.00%
Caisse de dépôt et placement du Québec (CDPQ)	12.62%
GIC Baker Street Investment Pte Ltd (11.20%) (an investment vehicle of GIC)	11.20%
Alinda QS Airports UK, LP (investment vehicle managed by Alinda Capital Partners),	11.18%
China Investment Corporation (CIC) Stable Investment Corporation (an investment vehicle of the China Investment Corporation)	10.00%
Universities Superannuation Scheme (USS) USS Buzzard Limited (wholly-owned by the Universities Superannuation Scheme)	10.00%

In 2019, Heathrow Airport reached a record of 80.9 million passengers, marking a +1% compared to 2018. From an initial analysis of Heathrow Airport Limited's financial statement¹⁴¹, Heathrow appears to be in good financial health. Revenues serve as an indicator of Heathrow's turnover growth, totaling almost £3 billion in 2019 (+3.5% compared to 2018, where revenues amounted to £2.8 billion). This growth was contributed to by the increase in passengers, supported by an infrastructure investment of £856 million.

These were realized through:

1. **Aeronautical Revenues:** Generated from fees charged to airlines for the use of airport facilities; these increased by a total of 4.9% compared to 2018 (£1.8 billion in 2019, £1.7 billion in 2018). The revenue per passenger increased by 3.9% to £22.64 (2018: £21.78).

¹⁴¹ The data has been taken from the *Annual Report and Financial Statement 2019*, at the following link: <https://www.heathrow.com/company/investor-centre/reports>

REVENUE

Year ended 31 December	2019 £m	2018 £m	Var %
Aeronautical	1,831	1,745	4.9
Retail	722	716	0.8
Other	423	413	2.4
Total revenue	2,976	2,874	3.5

2. **Non-Aeronautical Revenues:** These include concession fees from retail operators, parking proceeds, advertising income, rents from real estate spaces, and earnings from transport services, particularly the Heathrow Express rail service. Overall, these revenues increased by 0.8% compared to 2018 (£722 million in 2019, £716 million in 2018), with revenue per passenger remaining largely consistent.

As mentioned, "non-aeronautical" revenues stem from various services, primarily including:

- Concession fees from retail operators (+5.9%)
- Food and beverage services (+4.9%)
- Parking
- Other services

RETAIL REVENUE

Year ended 31 December	2019 £m	2018 £m	Var %
Retail concessions	342	323	5.9
Catering	64	61	4.9
Other retail	113	128	(11.7)
Car parking	125	126	(0.8)
Other services	78	78	0.0
Total retail revenue	722	716	0.8

In addition, these include:

- Rent from airport-owned spaces such as aircraft hangars, warehouses, cargo storage facilities, maintenance facilities, offices, and airline lounges (+4.5%)
- Provision of services such as baggage handling and passenger check-in.
- Fare revenues from the Heathrow Express rail service (+46.7%, attributed to a strong sustainability policy).

OTHER REVENUE

Year ended 31 December	2019 £m	2018 £m	Var %
Other regulated charges	239	243	(1.6)
Heathrow Express	22	15	46.7
Property and other	162	155	4.5
Total other revenue	423	413	2.4

The adjusted operating costs increased by 6.1% to £1.1 billion (2018: £1 billion), mainly due to the airport's expansion, security, and customer experience strategies. Moreover, Adjusted EBITDA increased by 2% (approximately £1.8 billion) compared to 2018 (£1.7 billion), and its post-tax profit increased by 41.5% to £631 million (2018: £446 million). This indicates how Heathrow achieved revenue growth while remaining efficient and tightly controlling operating costs. In fact, operating costs increased by only 5% in 2019. In 2019, the company raised £2.1 billion in global debt financing, including a £650 million 15-year bond issuance, demonstrating continued confidence from global investors in Heathrow's credit. The company also invested £620 million in various programs to enhance not only the passenger experience but also to meet new-generation safety requirements set by the Department for Transport (DFT), along with significant investments in passenger journey automation (self-bag drop¹⁴² and self-boarding gates in all terminals).

¹⁴² This is a new service that allows the traveler to independently check in their checked baggage, without requiring assistance from ground staff. This provides an advantage in terms of waiting time, reducing queues at check-in counters and making the journey to the landside area more streamlined.

Now that we have analyzed the financial statements of the two airports under study, another consideration becomes apparent: comparing airports uniformly is not straightforward, as airports often classify revenues differently. For example, in the cases examined, Heathrow classifies parking revenues as part of "*retail*" income, whereas at Changi Airport, it is categorized as "*other airport services*".

Heathrow's non-aeronautical revenues mainly include the following:

- Retail: concession fees from retail and commercial tenants and direct revenues from parking, advertising, etc.
- Other regulated charges: cost recovery for providing services such as baggage handling and passenger check-in counters.
- Heathrow Express: revenues from Heathrow Express rail service fares.
- Property: income from renting airport properties, such as aircraft hangars, warehouses, cargo storage facilities, maintenance facilities, airport offices, and airline lounges. As for Changi Airport, the three main revenue categories are as follows:
- Aviation services revenue: includes landing fees, parking fees, and air bridge fees for aircraft and fees for passenger services and security.
- Retail concessions and rental income: retail lease revenues or rental income from leasing airport properties.
- Other airport services: mainly includes cargo services revenue, franchise fees, utility fees, consulting fees, parking revenues, and other miscellaneous income. The following table attempts to compare, as much as possible, the growth of the two airports in the 2019 financial year compared to the previous year's financial statement (always starting from the different accounting principles in use):

Airport	Anno finanziario	TOT passengers	TOT Revenue (£)	TOT Non aeronautical revenue** (£)	EBITDA Adjusted (£)
Heathrow Airport	From January 1st to December 31st, 2019	80,9 millions	£ 3 billions <i>(+3.5% compared to the previous year)</i>	£ 1,1 billions <i>(+1,4% compared to the previous year)</i>	£ 1,8 billions <i>(+2% compared to the previous year)</i>
Changi Airport	From April 1st 2018 to March 31st 2019	66,3 millions	£ 1,7 billions* <i>(+16,8% compared to the previous year)</i>	£ 1 billions* <i>(+16,4% compared to the previous year)</i>	£ 0,8 billions* <i>(+12,3% compared to the previous year)</i>

**The exchange rate for Singapore dollar/ British pound on December 31, 2019 was: 0.564*

***In the "Non-aeronautical revenues" portion, all "revenue" items on the balance sheet were considered, excluding the "airport service" items.*

Chapter 3: Present and Future of Non-Aviation Business at Airports: Interviews

In this chapter, I conducted four interviews with experts in the non-aviation and airport travel retail sectors, who graciously agreed to answer questions regarding key aspects of the present and future of non-aviation business and travel retail.

I sought to delve into current topics with them, such as the recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic, as well as strategic matters that have become important for airport management companies—such as airport sustainability, products for sale, and technology—ultimately concluding with a vision for the future of this sector.

To advance this research, I reached out to industry experts in various domains to gather as comprehensive a view as possible, encompassing different perspectives. These ranged from Global CEOs of duty-free and travel retail multinational corporations to airport non-aviation managers, international experts in airport commercial area development, and journalists covering the travel retail and broader aviation sectors.

In the following paragraphs of this chapter, I have compiled the insights from these four interviews, categorizing them by topic of interest. The four interviews are available at the end of the project work in the '*Appendix*' section.

How did the non-aviation and travel retail sector react to the pandemic?

The world has recently emerged officially from the pandemic, and the airport sector, specifically travel retail, was dramatically impacted by Covid-19. There was not only a global reduction in sales but also a complete cash flow disruption in a very short period, traumatically, without having the time to formulate a response.

This naturally led to a series of more or less direct consequences. For Konstantinos Kouleris, an expert in non-aviation sector development, this unforeseen situation immediately prompted airport authorities and stakeholders working in the airport environment to decide to reduce their personnel. Airlines began suspending most flights, personnel salaries were reduced by at least 40%, and concessionaires—where shops in the terminals remained open—still reduced staff to a minimum.

For Kevin Rozario, a Forbes journalist covering travel retail, this aspect saw the reaction of national governments that provided support where possible, albeit in a disjointed manner from one country to another, during the darkest phase of the pandemic, through subsidies and furlough programs for travel retail workers. In many cases, operators had to resort to social safety nets, especially in the most critical phase, to try to save the industry, to maintain continuity in decisions and interventions in the initial post-Covid-19 phase, as seen in the case of Bergamo Milano Airport (Matteo Baù, Commercial Non-Aviation Director at Bergamo Milano Airport).

It should be noted that when the light began to reappear with the end of the pandemic, many companies seized the opportunity to rehire staff under more advantageous conditions and salaries for the company, in an effort to streamline the sector (Kouleris). The effects of the pandemic undoubtedly caused irreparable damage; however, Andrea Belardini, CEO of Dufry, is convinced that all of this will leave a very important signal of progress in the long term. There have been clear and distinct phenomena:

1. The need to create resilience: Operators still present in the sector after the pandemic tsunami had to focus first and foremost on ensuring survival through strict discipline in

cash flow control, cost reduction, in a context, of course, involving proactive management of the entire stakeholder system ranging from suppliers to airport operators. This phenomenon was also highlighted by Kouleris in a more circumscribed manner, while Belardini's perspective concerns a cohesive effort by all stakeholders—airport operators, retailers, brands—to make the business sustainable in the future.

2. Risk management in contracts with concessionaires, i.e., leases. The post-pandemic period allowed the consideration of uncertainty as an indispensable value in the evaluation of partnerships and greater flexibility in lease contract management: a convergence was found between infrastructure operators and retail operators toward a more sustainable and balanced risk management. In many cases, derogations were applied to existing contracts within the so-called “*trinity*” (Infrastructure Operators, Brands, and Retailers), demonstrating a strong inclination toward partnership. For Kouleris, this means an extension of one or two years to the contract duration, revoking unprofitable concessions consensually, re-establishing a stable commercial relationship among stakeholders to the previous state.

These are two of the main response phenomena to the pandemic that emerged in the early post-Covid phase, developing antibodies and crisis management know-how in the sector. In the post-Covid period, as airport traffic began to recover, a recovery in revenues was observed, albeit unevenly, varying from region to region and by local openings. For example, geographical areas like North America and the Caribbean, along with some tourist destinations, had already reached pre-2019 levels in 2021 (Belardini).

However, as emphasized by Matteo Baù, some responses (mostly political but also strategic) were belated and inefficient: this was the case for various airports in Northern Europe that saw a 25% reduction in capacity.

The other side of the coin is what Rozario defines as '*revenge spending*': airport retailers began rehiring store staff at a rapid pace to meet the high passenger demand, higher than expected, and also invested in store renovations to increase revenue per passenger. The same kind of

intervention happened, for example, at Bergamo Milano Airport, which ensured an almost unexpected recovery in terms of cash flows (Baù).

One last aspect analyzed by Belardini in this sector's restart phase was the evolution of the supply chain concept with a greater focus on demand forecasting. Here too, there was a huge disruption with the onset of the pandemic, for two fundamental reasons:

1. Firstly, the reduction in transport capacity, especially by sea, to long destinations such as Asia and America. The lack—or significant reduction—of this capacity led to a significant increase in costs and *lead times* (delivery times). The need and ability to find slots to transport goods more efficiently emerged as a result.
2. Secondly, the impact of the end of the pandemic created lasting effects on certain categories of travel retail: the creation of more resilient supply chains with a greater focus on forecasting and a more integrated relationship in the exchange of information with suppliers, precisely to ensure visibility of needs to ensure a continuous and adequate flow of goods.

In conclusion, analyzing the words of the four interviewed experts, efforts are being made to return to normalcy or at least to get back on the right track through necessary interventions not to disrupt but to optimize processes in a sector that, before Covid, experienced a strong upward trajectory for about 30 years.

Consumer Behavior: Differences between the Pre and Post-Covid Phases

Another phenomenon that emerged in the sector due to the disruption caused by Covid-19 was the need, initially, and then the time, to rethink the business model: all stakeholders had to reset and start asking themselves the right questions from the consumer's perspective, according to Belardini, with a view to identifying the *value proposition*¹⁴³:

"Now people are not traveling, and we are not generating revenues; will they travel again? Will they maintain the same purchasing habits as before? Will they buy in the same way as before?"

Obviously, clear trends emerged with the answers to these questions that needed to be addressed.

In the immediate post-pandemic period, a younger airport consumer profile was observed compared to the previous phase, mainly due to the more leisure-oriented type of travel (Belardini). The *millennial* and *Generation Z* trend was well known even before the pandemic and was already part of the marketing and commercial assortment plans of European operators, but Covid-19 accelerated this trend.

Rozario goes into even more detail and emphasizes how the "new consumers/travelers in this phase increased their per capita budget, probably resulting from greater purchasing power or as a reaction to what he has termed '*revenge spending*', which is more related to the psychological aspect, a consideration also noted by Baù in the case of Bergamo Milano Airport.

Kouleris, on the other hand, approaches it from a different perspective than Belardini and Rozario: the behavior of the airport consumer remained the same between the pre and post-Covid periods. Regardless of the pandemic situation, passengers always want to enjoy the airport

¹⁴³ The value proposition is a key concept in the field of marketing and business. It represents the unique set of benefits and values that a company or a product offers to its customers to meet their needs and solve their problems better than the competition.

The value proposition focuses on what makes a company, product, or service unique and appealing to the target customer. It is the distinctive element that convinces customers to choose one option over others in the market.

and flight *experience* to the fullest, so they expect a normalization of the experience. The only differences Kouleris noticed were at the structural level—in the health prevention measures implemented by airports, and the consequent reaction of passengers to this 'new' situation—which was still appreciated and generated a sense of trust and relaxation, essential requirements linked to purchasing behavior.

Rozario still believes that over time, travel will *normalize*, and the direct consequence of this situation will also be that spending patterns will stabilize.

For Kouleris, the emerging opportunities for the travel retail environment are fundamentally related to technological advancements, such as contactless purchases. This brings us to the second behavioral trend also analyzed by Belardini, i.e., an increasingly connected consumer.

Lockdowns, in general, have brought a much larger audience of consumers, across many more categories, to engage with online business, both by making *late adopters* familiar with online shopping and by increasing the adoption of the e-commerce channel to simplify and enhance penetration (Belardini).

In the practical case of Bergamo Milano Airport, Baù acknowledges that changes in consumer behavior have been significant and, in part, unexpected. The end of last year showed an incredible +50% in revenues compared to the previous year, due to a series of factors, including primarily the emotional/psychological aspect: a desire to spend 'regardless,' driven by the reopening of the sector after restrictions, in line with what Rozario calls '*revenge spending*'. In some cases, this factor alone would not have had such a clear effect if not parallelly associated with a series of infrastructure upgrades and modernization of terminal spaces.

In essence, Covid-19 has disrupted the behaviors of all the key players in the sector, both in terms of preferences and purchasing decisions.

However, in this aspect as well, all interviewees agree in foreseeing a physiological decline in this behavior towards 'normalization' in the near future.

Technology and Digital Transformation in Airports and Travel Retail

Digital transformation in airports is an ongoing process that has been significantly accelerated by the pandemic, enabling a reduction in the time spent on *landside activities* (check-in, baggage handling, security checks, and passport control), thereby conserving more time for *dwell time* in the commercial zone.

Undoubtedly, digitalization has been and continues to be one of the strategies that have been enhanced in this early post-Covid_19 phase, and it is a strategy that will solidify in the near future (Baù).

However, digital adoption is challenging in an infrastructure like airports, where many operators have different yet often integrated roles (Belardini). This challenge, according to Baù, arises from both market and generational demands.

When discussing airport *digital transformation*, one must consider not only a series of broader improvements to infrastructure and mandatory processes but also a shift towards digitalization in travel retail with a focus on user experience (Belardini).

From an infrastructural and process perspective, Kouleris is convinced that technology can certainly help minimize the time required for security checks, baggage delivery, and immigration check. For instance, at Hamad International Airport, there are digital passport and boarding pass screening supports for faster processing. There are also live maps in the official app to improve the *customer journey* by offering peace of mind, relaxation, and additional time for shopping.

Online check-in is another process that reduces time and simultaneously allows the storage of a range of passenger data that—subject to privacy and other factors—would generate audience profiling and segmentation. However, in some cases, through online check-in, it is the airline that tracks the passenger, and the paradox is that the airport operator might not even know that the passenger is passing through the terminal (Baù).

In terms of travel retail, technology and digital penetration now play a fundamental role, although they arrived much later compared to other markets, primarily because the travel retail channel relies mostly on agreements with suppliers that do not allow home delivery, with some exceptions.

Among the technological solutions significantly impacting *user experience*, geofencing applications are worth mentioning. They calculate the volume or number of passengers entering specific areas or retail stores or gate lounges, which are very useful for collecting data for further analysis and improvements for airport and retail operations (Kouleris).

In this phase, airport operators, including Dufry, are pushing strongly for the creation of a 360-degree digital interaction. It has been understood that visibility on digital platforms before purchase significantly impacts the creation of a more intimate relationship with the consumer (Belardini).

Such technology enables retailers to track passengers from home to the departure gate and send them messages at the right points of their journey to remind them of special offers in a nearby store, for example. Passengers can also *click and collect* products, ensuring a sale for retailers before the traveler even enters the airport (Rozario).

According to Belardini, to create greater interest in digital interaction, one must constantly adapt what is defined as "*user experience*", creating actual value for the consumer. With digital tools, continuous contact can be offered to accompany the consumer in their choices or help optimize decision times (e.g., virtually trying different lipstick colors on the taxi ride to the airport).

From a digital marketing perspective, with all the methods available today, such as *programmatic advertising*, *social media*, and more, engaging with consumers through various channels has become much more efficient and cost-effective.

Among the commonly used tools, many airports are investing in creating e-commerce, i.e., online spaces to then pick up the product directly at the airport. Click-and-collect, mentioned earlier, is

one of the most common in travel retail, as it is the easiest to set up. Brands test digital promotions using the "opportunities" that arise through social media to attract Gen Z.

This aligns with the fact that many people are starting to become familiar with online shopping (as a consequence of the lockdown, including what Belardini defines as late adopters) and pick up their purchases from physical stores, mainly because many of these products are offered at highly discounted prices online.

However, there is a flip side to this rising trend, which Kouleris believes needs to be considered now before it's too late. It's necessary to integrate a physical location at the airport for collecting pre-orders because e-commerce is becoming a strong trend in the airport environment day by day, and it is estimated to increase by 30% over the next five years.

Then there is the creation of the "*phygital*"¹⁴⁴ offering, which is equally important (Rozario). Completely online shopping was considered essential during the pandemic, but now its strength has somewhat diminished as consumers like to enter physical environments, as also shared by Kouleris. Through the *phygital channel*, there is the possibility of maintaining a parallel online market while using the wealth of data collected from the technologies used to better analyze customer preferences, behaviors, and habits, all with a view to optimizing marketing strategies.

¹⁴⁴ *Phygital* means combining the best components of the online experience with those of the offline experience to create a new type of experience where the two worlds (digital and physical) coexist within the same space and feed off each other to generate a personalized, interactive, and engaging experience. Any consumer space (in this case, the airport) can become phygital if digital technologies are implemented inside it that can bring about significant changes in the customer experience.

A phygital experience is based on three essential elements, commonly referred to in the industry as the three "i's" of phygital: immediacy, immersion, and interaction. The main advantage for companies is that they can use the vast amount of data collected by technologies used in phygital to better analyze the preferences, behaviors, and habits of on-site customers.

These data, in addition to being used to improve the phygital experience itself, can be added to data collected in other company channels to create a comprehensive database that allows for continuous optimization of marketing strategies in an omnichannel perspective.

Even the concept of parking, as another channel of non-aviation business supported by digital transformation, has optimized and improved cash flows. For example, in the case of Bergamo Milano Airport, this has always been one of the main non-aviation core businesses, and in the last year, it has doubled its revenues thanks to digitalization efforts that started around 15 years ago (Baù).

Another heavily used tool in travel retail after the "digital revolution" is loyalty programs. Technology through loyalty cards also means easy access to passenger data (e.g., spending habits) that can be used to modify the purchase offering at the airport or target specific offers to each passenger, just like supermarkets already do (Rozario).

Every day, therefore, new technologies, improvements to existing and innovative supports are easing the entire process from arrival at the airport to boarding, thereby offering more time for passengers to shop (Kouleris). However, it should be noted that this surge of digital transformation benefits observed during the initial post-Covid_19 phase is not unstoppable. Baù already sees a slowdown compared to the significant results of the past year, which is heading—also in this context—towards a phase of normalization.

Does security impact non-aviation business revenues?

Security is a sensitive topic in airport infrastructure, influencing both the travel journey, the traveler's path through various control phases mainly in the landside area, and the travel retail perspective, particularly in the airside zone where the traveler becomes a potential consumer. Security also becomes a psychological factor influencing the traveler's purchase decisions and behaviors.

Especially with the advent of the pandemic, airport security has become even more critical, revealing uncertainties in this historical period from various perspectives, including passenger safety, equipment, and structures.

Historically, there has always been a conflict between the security department and the commercial department at the airport. The commercial departments continuously seek additional spaces to develop more sales activities, hence generate more revenue. Conversely, security restrictions act as a brake on commercial development (Kouleris).

This conflict or quest for balance stems from the fact that all studies converge on the idea that security directly impacts travel retail. Long queues for control operations can reduce the time spent in shops and, at the same time, negatively affect passengers' mood and, consequently, their likelihood to make purchases (Rozario).

It is almost impossible, according to Kouleris, to avoid or ignore safety rules and restrictions. This represents a significant challenge to find a balance between the two forces, a balance that is always found where there is a common understanding between safety rules and commercial development, with the primary objective being passenger satisfaction.

Security constraints are linked, for example, to the width of corridors for passenger circulation, the form of various units, the areas that the commercial department aims to develop for travel retail, and even advertising spaces, which can be problematic if the advertisements cause confusion or provide misleading information (Kouleris).

For this reason, in many cases at airports, a "decompression" area has been planned, a physical space for passage between the security area and duty-free shops, allowing passengers to organize themselves before entering the shops (Rozario). This distinctly separates the two phases of the airport customer journey, allowing emotional recovery that reduces the stress level of mandatory checks and emotionally prepares the traveler to move from the landside area (commercial) with a more relaxed approach, fundamental to a consumer's predisposition to purchase.

The concept of optimizing airport transit times and the overall qualification of the travel experience linked to a more predisposed attitude is also addressed by Belardini, but from a different perspective, namely, associated with the role of technology.

Thanks to continuous improvement, transit times between landside and airside are progressively decreasing, despite specific critical situations, mainly due to difficulties in sourcing personnel following the pandemic.

Therefore, technology has a positive impact on the dwell time. The question to ask is whether this dwell time will be dedicated to arriving a little later at the airport or spending more time in the commercial area. In any case, it will undoubtedly be a change that improves the situation. In this regard, technologies such as integrated online check-in, as already experimented in Milan and Rome, as emphasized by Baù, will allow all involved operators to benefit from it.

Airport Sustainability and in Travel Retail

In recent years, most international airports have shown great attention to environmental sustainability, pursuing *carbon neutrality goals*. For example, London Heathrow has led the way, declaring its ambition to become the world's first "zero carbon airport" by the mid-2030s. Regardless of this clear and impactful strategy, airports worldwide have adopted modernization plans with a "greener" direction in choices and consumption.

One example is the plastic-free policy in the retail sector, compelling commercial partners to reduce or even eliminate the use of plastic in packaging or products, as witnessed at Bergamo Milano Airport (Baù).

Furthermore, the corporate world has seen a significant acceleration towards the broader scope of ESG (Environmental, Social, Corporate Governance). Investors and clients now demonstrate more interest and expectations in this regard (Belardini). Many operators are investing in more responsible policies, such as solutions for energy efficiency, including investments in low-consumption lighting technologies or the use of renewable energy. Rationalization of transportation and supply chain efficiency are also part of this trend. Finally, there is a commitment to establishing governance systems towards consumers and employees and defining, measuring, and monitoring objectives (Belardini).

This now well-established sensitivity to environmental concerns has led airport management companies to align themselves by organizing training and updates for all infrastructure personnel. International passengers frequenting the airport are highly attentive to this issue, so workers in travel retail must be aligned or adequately prepared for specific demands (Kouleris). The same applies to all sustainability and social impact matters. Only through consistent investments in the sector by airport management can awareness be developed and strengthened.

From a strategic communication perspective, this can lead to special awards globally, such as those by Skytrax¹⁴⁵.

Rozario also confirms that the majority of airport travel retail stores are adopting a sustainability position. However, the effectiveness and validity of these positions remain debatable. Regarding the "green" concept, it should be noted that internationally, it has in some cases become a kind of trend to follow rather than active policies (Baù).

Among the major names credibly acting in airport retail, Lagardere Travel Retail and Heinemann likely lead the sector in this regard, along with Dufry, concerning store setups and brand selections that meet sustainability criteria.

In conclusion, Covid-19 has taught us to be more reflective both as global citizens and consumers. The environmental issue is a cultural and inevitable process that will yield tangible results not before a decade. The feeling is that it will be a true added value to the sector when the new generations (Millennials and Gen Z) become the main audience making thoughtful choices, even in their purchasing decisions (Baù).

¹⁴⁵ Skytrax is a UK-based research company established in 1989 that operates in the field of civil aviation. In 1999, the company introduced the "World Airline and Airport Star Rating" program, an international rating system that ranks airlines and airports based on product quality and service standards. Skytrax is also among the most renowned global organizations in the sector for awarding annual recognitions in various categories.

Future Trends in Non-Aviation Business and Travel Retail

The last topic discussed in the interviews revolves around current trends and the prediction of future trends in travel retail, and more generally, the direction non-aviation business is heading. It should be highlighted that this topic, more than others, has generated different viewpoints among the four interviewees, likely influenced by their diverse roles and areas of involvement in the sector.

We must start from a fixed point, that in this world, nothing remains static; everything is in continuous evolution. If we look at the profile of travel retail categories now and 10/15 years ago, there hasn't been a total revolution, but undoubtedly, there have been some enduring trends.

Luxury, for example, is increasingly present both from the perspective of brand investments and airport operators' investments within the travel retail channel, services, and much more (Belardini). Currently, luxury goods are performing exceptionally well, possibly as a post-pandemic reaction, and the prediction is that they might experience a slight dip. However, with Chinese travelers now returning, luxury brands will remain a stronghold in travel retail in the coming years, a view also shared by Kouleris.

Another significant genre that has been present for a long time and has gained considerable success in recent years is that of local products, such as crafts and food (Belardini). This opinion is also shared by Baù, who, however, narrows down high-quality food as a trend that remains particularly popular in the travel retail domain.

Another category that is an evergreen in travel retail, especially in duty-free shops, is that of spirits and fragrances (Belardini), due to tax convenience.

The concept of wellness is still underdeveloped in airports but is a growing trend, with Changi Airport leading the way. Travelers are seeking personal relaxation and a bit of luxury (Kouleris). However, wellness isn't just about relaxation, but also about products: there is increasing attention to *holistic health* and *wellbeing*, leading to more purchases of items that promote overall well-being and personal happiness. This was one of the first areas where many operators

intervened, generating changes in both consumer preferences and consumption habits: value proposition, which goes beyond the purchase and makes the product appealing to the customer (Belardini). For instance, Dufry has introduced the concept of "*mind body soul*"¹⁴⁶, a shop-in-shop offering a range of products addressing wellness needs, from skincare to vitamins and supplements. Investments were made to give greater visibility to products with a higher sustainability gradient. Consumers reacted by rewarding this choice, directing them towards more responsible purchasing.

There has also been a significant acceleration in sales in the electronics sector, a category that has garnered much interest from travelers for its convenience (Belardini), considering the increasing digitalization of consumers, even *late adopters*.

An aspect to emphasize when discussing travel retail trends is digitization. Current trends in the industry are linked to the digitalization of purchases, a simple purchasing process, and the development of a one-stop-shop, ideal for travelers (Kouleris). According to Belardini, this is a chapter where the sprint over the next 5 years will be massive, both because affordable tools are now available and because consumers expect this kind of interaction: entering a store and making most purchases while enjoying all the advantages of technology. This is the trend that Kouleris also believes will dominate the near future, without forgetting the importance of traditional shopping, which will remain a necessity, as travelers enjoy physical contact and spending time in retail stores *to kill time*.

In a more general sense, we can say that the sector has reached a significant level of maturity, a result of combined investments by all involved players (airports, brands, and operators): dedicated retail spaces, flow planning, airport design, and the choice of retail categories. Today, all of this has reached quite high levels of optimization (Belardini).

¹⁴⁶ DUFREY, *Dufry introduces Mind, Body and Soul shop-in-shop concept at Queen Alia International Airport*, <https://www.dufry.com/en/news/2022-10-19/dufry-introduces-mind-body-and-soul-shop-shop-concept-queen-alia-international>, 19 October 2022

However, the other fundamental aspect that will build the foundations of the future of the non-aviation sector in an increasingly digitized and interconnected infrastructure like the airport is user experience. Hence, there will be investments from both brands and operators to integrate entertainment into the act of purchase, converging various categories like retail and food & beverage (Belardini).

One more consideration at this point concerns brands: excluding luxury brands, which have a separate market as we have seen, fashion leads certain specific brands to have a significant market in travel retail, but limited to the current fashion trends, which may be replaced by another brand after a few years (Baù).

As Rozario emphasizes, to achieve this kind of stability, the *airport concession model* will also need to change to democratize travel retail and open up to traditional and new brands. In this way, more passengers can make purchases, and the retail environment can become more diverse and interesting. This diverse choice is what has been lacking in travel retail so far.

In conclusion, it must be reiterated that products are constantly evolving. If we look at airports with a critical mass in terms of size, we find a huge variety in terms of the range of products. Some products are and will always be challenging to display in an airport context (except for display purposes), but anything that can be taken away can become part of travel retail, thanks to increasing attention to adapting terminal design to create real shopping experiences (Belardini).

Conclusion

The non-aviation business of airports is undergoing significant evolution—an evolution that began before the pandemic and was accelerated by Covid-19—and is increasingly important in the global economy. The modern airport is no longer just a transit point for passengers but a multifunctional hub offering a wide range of services and activities.

This evolution of the airport sector has seen an increase in dependency on non-aeronautical or commercial revenues, attributed to various factors outlined in the preceding chapters. For instance, consider that in 2017, travel retail alone reached 40 billion dollars¹⁴⁷.

Over the last approximately 15 years, the *aviation* sector has been challenged to respond to a series of "commercial" pressures that could have jeopardized the future survival of a number of airports. Particularly, the decline in *aviation revenues* and the abolition of taxes and fees within the European aviation landscape significantly limited the profit-generating capacity of many airport entities (in 2018 alone, according to ACI Europe, 47% of European airports lost money¹⁴⁸).

Moreover, in recent decades, a structural shift has been observed in the airport sector, including changes in funding, control, and management of airports. Privatization (particularly strong in Europe, less so in the United States) has propelled the development of more diversified commercial policies with a *business-oriented approach*. We rapidly transitioned from an average of about 30% of non-aviation revenues in airports' balance sheets in 1990 to approximately 50% in 2007 according to the 2007 ACI report¹⁴⁹. Much of this expansion is attributed to travel retail and the corresponding increase in dedicated spaces within terminals.

In the realm of airport shopping, the passenger interacts with three different key players that influence their personal travel experience: the airline, the airport management company, and the

¹⁴⁷ Steve Cameron, *Sneaky Ways Airports Get You To Spend Money*, <https://www.businessinsider.com/airports-spend-more-money-duty-free-shopping-restaurants-2019-8?r=US&IR=T>, 2019

¹⁴⁸ ACI Europe, <https://www.aci-europe.org/>

¹⁴⁹ ACI - Airport Council International, <https://aci.aero/>

retailer, each with a distinct role in what is termed the customer experience, significantly impacting airport revenues.

As a general rule, these actors often operate independently because their business models are not always aligned. The passenger does not concern themselves with these kinds of issues, as their objective is to smoothly reach the boarding gate with a relaxed and untroubled state of mind, regardless of the type of journey they are embarking on (leisure or business). However, during this obligatory journey, passengers are surrounded by a series of external stimuli that also lead them to make purchases (of any kind) with a predisposed mental state. The travel retail environment indeed encourages passengers to make less planned purchases compared to the planned purchasing behavior that underlies traditional retail¹⁵⁰, thus transforming the airport infrastructure into a unique commercial space.

A more integrated approach among airlines, airport management companies, and retailers would provide passengers with a more complete and dynamic experience, and at the same time, would undoubtedly lead to even more efficient total revenue development. This was observed by analyzing privately managed airports, such as Heathrow in London, that combine various areas of intervention.

In defense of this global sector—which nevertheless encompasses an infinity of variables to consider, including various airport management modalities, national development policies, airport types, management-improvement interventions, geographical-cultural aspects, and the airport's strategic position, to name a few—Covid-19 brought an unexpected massive disruption, leaving no time to prepare a reaction. Undoubtedly, it is one of the sectors that has been hit the hardest by the pandemic and the effects of the lockdown. There has not only been a reduction in flights and airport sales but a complete cessation of cash generation within a very short time.

¹⁵⁰ Omar Ogenyi, *Airport Retailing: Examining Airline Passengers' Impulsive Shopping Behaviour*, in *Journal of Euromarketing*, s.l., Taylor & Francis Online, 2001

This, of course, has compelled all operators to adopt timely and radical measures, completely rethinking the business model and developing the know-how and antibodies to face a crisis of this magnitude, even in the future.

From the analysis presented in this project work, at least three characteristics have emerged post-Covid-19:

- Firstly, a change in consumer purchasing behavior facilitated by digitalization, which saw an acceleration of results in the early post-pandemic period. Although it is impossible to predict the impact this digital transformation will have on travel retail in the coming years, millennials who have grown up with e-commerce will expect to experience the same level of flexibility in their airport purchases as they do at home. The use of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, the *internet of things*, and *big data* is enabling airports to improve operational efficiency while offering more personalized services that enhance consumer loyalty. By combining the capabilities of traditional retail and e-commerce, as is already happening in many airports, revenues could significantly increase.
- The expansion of commercial space in airports represents a radical shift in non-aviation revenues. The growing demand for high-quality services and products by passengers has led to significant investments in non-aviation infrastructure. The development of new spaces necessitates innovative and technological solutions to ensure good revenue outcomes and has become an essential line not only for the survival of the airport but also for its success.
- A growing focus on environmental and social sustainability in airports. Eco-sustainable initiatives, the implementation of low-impact technologies, the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, and the adoption of socially responsible business practices not only contribute to environmental protection but also enhance the airport's image and create a competitive advantage in the market.

In a global, globalized, and increasingly interconnected context like the airport sector, management companies are exploring various ways to retain and attract not only national and

international passengers (with the latter having greater purchasing power) but also more international airlines (which is obviously an advantage for airports that are also hubs, such as Heathrow).

Airports are also attempting to attract non-airport customers by creating unique experiences with art galleries, concert spaces, and theme parks. As seen in the case of Changi Airport in Singapore, one of the emerging international trends in the non-aviation business is a particular focus on local communities, which become a new target audience and can use the airport—the landside area—as an alternative shopping center, especially if easily accessible with good road and rail connections. In the case of Frankfurt Airport, residents are encouraged to shop at the airport thanks to free parking and extended opening hours compared to traditional shopping centers.

In conclusion, it is incontrovertible from this project work that the non-aviation business offers significant profit opportunities that were not so clear a few decades ago. Sectors such as retail, food & beverage, hospitality, real estate services, tourism, entertainment, and cultural activities are gaining more and more space in airport terminals. This fact registers another directly related consequence: the reduction of dependence on income from air traffic, especially in times of economic instability and fluctuations in the aviation industry.

In the near future, in my opinion, digital transformation will continue to be the true driving force of this sector, advancing to higher levels, with greater integration between various landside-airside processes to offer even more innovative and engaging services to passengers.

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Appendix

Interview with Andrea Belardini

Chief Executive Officer, Division Asia, Middle East, and Australia, Member of the Executive Committee at Dufry. From 1997 to 2000, he held various top positions at Carlson Wagonlit Travel: first as Controller and Project Manager, then as Director of Operations Italy and Vice President of Operations South Europe. From 2000 to 2004, he was Executive Vice President Strategy & Development at Aeroporti di Roma, and from 2004 to 2009, Executive Vice President Commercial Business Management & Development. From 2009 to 2015, he was Chief Executive Officer Europe at Nuance Group, also holding the position of Global Chief Commercial Officer from 2013 onwards.

Dr. Belardini, we have recently emerged from the pandemic, and the airport sector in general (and consequently the non-aviation business) has not only faced major restrictions but also a drastic drop in revenue. What kind of impact did this have, and what strategies have been implemented during this initial recovery phase?

The airport sector in general and travel retail specifically were dramatically impacted by the pandemic. Not only did we see a reduction in sales, but also a complete interruption of cash generation in a very short period, forcing operators to adopt timely and radical measures. This crisis in the sector had a strong short-term impact, but I believe that in the long run, it will leave a very important mark of progress. Looking at the data published by operators, we have already returned to pre-COVID sales levels in most markets. Per-passenger spending is solidly increasing, and operators are becoming more agile. There were clear and distinct phenomena, for example: the first being the need to create resilience. The operators still present in the sector after the pandemic storm had to focus on ensuring survival through rigorous cash flow control and cost reduction, in a context of proactive management involving all stakeholders, from suppliers to airport operators. I must say that, overall, this challenge has been positive for all the

players in the airport travel retail chain because both airport operators, retailers, and brands made efforts to support each other to make the business sustainable in the future. So, as mentioned, the first element to emphasize was the creation of resilience, which will undoubtedly leave positive impacts. Those who were in the sector at that time not only developed the necessary muscles but also the ability to manage the crisis in terms of know-how. Another important theme, which will have a lasting effect, is risk management in contracts with concessionaires (i.e., leases). There was a convergence between infrastructure operators and retail operators towards a more sustainable and balanced risk management approach, and in many cases, exceptions were made to existing contracts, within the so-called "trinity" (Infrastructure Operators, Brands, and Retailers), demonstrating a strong inclination towards partnership. The third element that had a strong impact in the world of travel retail is undoubtedly supply chain management.

What happened, then, with the supply chain?

The global supply chain of the travel retail channel suffered for two main reasons. Firstly, the reduction in transport capacity, especially by sea, to long-haul destinations like Asia and America. There was a significant reduction or complete absence of this capacity, leading to an unprecedented increase in costs and waiting times. Then, the post-pandemic impact resulted in reduced capacity in glass and paper production, reducing the fill rate from suppliers. It was necessary to create more resilient supply chains with a greater focus on demand forecasting and an integrated relationship in the exchange of information with suppliers, to ensure visibility of needs and minimize stock interruptions.

Do you see any other evolutionary trends in the sector that emerged during this phase? For example, from the perspective of consumer behavior, have you noticed any changes between pre and post-COVID?

Yes, undoubtedly another phenomenon that, in my opinion, emerged from this disruption caused by COVID-19 is the need for and subsequently the time to rethink the model: to ask the right questions about where travel habits and consumption habits were heading. Many operators in travel retail have redefined their business model, starting with identifying the value

proposition. The questions we all asked were: "*When and how will people start traveling again? Will they maintain the same buying habits as before? Will they buy in the same way they used to?*" Obviously, the answers to these questions revealed clear trends that needed to be addressed. Firstly, a younger consumer profile: during the pandemic and in its immediate aftermath, we noticed a slightly younger population, also due to a type of leisure-oriented travel. The increasing influence of millennials and Generation Z was well known even before the pandemic, and was already part of the marketing plans and commercial assortment of European operators, but the pandemic accelerated this trend even further. The second trend was that of a more connected consumer, a real push towards digitization. The lockdown brought a much wider audience of consumers, and across many more categories, to engage with online business, making consumers less inclined (late adopters) now familiar with online shopping and digital platforms in general. Even in terms of preferences and purchasing decisions, COVID-19 disrupted all key players in the sector, from operators to consumers. It taught us to be more reflective both as global citizens and as consumers.

Do you think this also ties into the concept of environmental sustainability applied to travel retail?

The theme of sustainability has become more embedded in actual consumption choices. As I mentioned earlier, COVID-19 taught us to be more reflective both as global citizens and as consumers. But undoubtedly, sustainability does not only refer to the brand's DNA, the nature of products, and packaging; there is more attention to holistic wellness and well-being, therefore more purchases for things that generate personal well-being and happiness. This was one of the first areas many operators intervened in: the value proposition, meaning that value that goes beyond the purchase and makes the product attractive to the customer. And it generated changes both in terms of consumer preferences and consumption habits (more online purchases, preferences in certain categories, and much more). Moreover, in the corporate world, there has been a significant acceleration towards the theme of ESG (Environmental, Social, Corporate Governance), with investors and clients showing more interest and expectations.

Will this behavior continue to evolve?

Let's start from a fixed point, meaning that in this world, nothing is not in continuous evolution. If we look at the profile of travel retail categories now and 10/15 years ago, we haven't seen a total revolution, but undoubtedly some trends have emerged that still persist: luxury, for example, is increasingly present, both from the perspective of brand investments and airport operator investments within the travel retail channel, in services, and much more.

But returning to the impact on the consumer, we saw some important things that translated into choices by airport operators: the first is adjusting the offer (increased demand for more sustainable products, requiring greater integration and cooperation with brands to give more space to products with certain "green" characteristics, from packaging to material origin); in the health and wellness sector, for example, with Dufry, we had launched the concept of "mind body soul¹⁵¹", which is a shop-in-shop where we create a choice for the consumer, grouping a series of products that address the need for wellness, taking care of oneself with different categories and local products ranging from skincare to vitamins, supplements. On this, we invested in giving greater visibility, through dedicated spaces and effective in-store communication, to products with a higher sustainability gradient. And we saw that where we communicated the concept of sustainability better, the consumer reacted by rewarding the choice: all this simply by better directing the consumer towards greater awareness of responsible purchasing.

We have talked so far about the "physical place" of the airport. How do you think technology can further transform travel retail?

Travel retail is a sector where digital penetration now plays a fundamental role. It arrived very late compared to other markets, especially because the travel retail channel is mostly based on agreements with suppliers that do not allow home delivery. There are exceptions for some marginal categories, but in general, the main business of our sector involves pickup at the airport and often in the "sterile" area, limiting the opportunity to generate "usage frequency" outside

¹⁵¹ DUFREY, Dufry introduces Mind, Body and Soul shop-in-shop concept at Queen Alia International Airport, <https://www.dufry.com/en/news/2022-10-19/dufry-introduces-mind-body-and-soul-shop-shop-concept-queen-alia-international>, 19 October 2022

the travel moment and limiting the convenience of pure e-commerce. Having said that, the evolution of digital solutions is undergoing a strong transformation even in the travel retail channel. In this phase, we are witnessing airport operators, including Dufry, pushing strongly towards creating a 360-degree digital interaction because it has been understood that visibility on digital platforms before purchase greatly influences the creation of a more intimate relationship with the consumer. From a digital marketing point of view, with all the tools available today such as programmatic advertising, social media, and much more, it has become much more efficient and cost-effective to engage with consumers in various channels. To create greater interest in digital interaction, one must constantly adapt what is defined as the "user experience," both online and in stores, and create real value for the consumer. With digital tools, continuous contact can be offered to accompany the consumer in choices (for example, providing digital information about the various base fragrances that make up a perfume), or helping them optimize choice times (for example, virtually trying on different lipstick colors while traveling in a taxi to the airport), and pre-order a product to be conveniently picked up before boarding.

Can you tell us more?

The theme of further development concerns loyalty management. Smartphone app solutions allow consumers to carry with them a wide range of benefits, from e-commerce functionalities, to "augmented experience," to sharing and exchanging benefits with other loyalty programs (e.g., airlines), to electronic payment systems, and more. In other words, the revolution happening in this period by sector operators and airport operators is to invest now in strengthening digital engagement, even if e-commerce in travel retail is not necessarily measured in terms of success by online sales: what is more important is the type of interaction and the type of support that technology can offer to the shopping experience.

So, how do you see the ongoing digital transformation in this sector?

I am convinced that in the next 2-3 years, we will see an exponential change thanks to improvements in user experience, better content, more involvement of travel ecosystem actors, and greater active participation from brands.

The theme of airport security. It has always been a topic that has influenced development strategies for airport travel retail, especially related to uncertainty in the timing to the boarding gate.

Security has always been central in the airport context, a relevant theme in terms of optimizing airport crossing times and the overall qualification of the travel experience. Technology is continuously improving in this regard, along with the processes, resulting in progressively reduced crossing times between the so-called landside and airside areas (before and after security checks). These times are gradually reducing (although specific critical situations remain, especially due to difficulties in finding staff following the pandemic). There are cases in Rome and Milan, for example, that are testing these new machines that do not require the physical separation of computers and liquids during security checks, significantly reducing waiting times and significantly improving the experience. It can be said with certainty that technology is continuously improving to reduce crossing times.

And this, of course, also affects what is defined as the "dwell time."

Exactly, the question to ask, however, is whether this dwell time will be spent arriving a little later at the airport or spending more time in the commercial area of the airport. But it will certainly be a change that will improve the situation because there will still be those who take advantage of it to spend more time at the airport, and those who arrive in the airside commercial area with a definitely more predisposed mindset, which is also good for the shopping experience.

Returning to the theme of environmental impact, this time in terms of airport infrastructure, what direction is being taken?

There are three/four areas in which progress is being made. There is the aspect of the impact on the planet (Environment), on which many operators are investing in more responsible

policies. Of great relevance are solutions for energy efficiency, so investments, for example, in lighting technologies with lower consumption or resorting to renewable energies. Another area receiving much attention is the rationalization of transportation and supply chain efficiency. Then, there is also the aspect of sustainability towards consumers and employees, and the commitment to establish governance systems that allow defining, measuring, and monitoring objectives.

A question about the current and future trends of travel retail, from an expert in the field from every point of view. According to you, what are the trends that are gaining popularity now?

We can say that the sector has reached a significant level of maturity due to the combined effect of the investment of all players involved, namely airports, brands, and operators: dedicated retail spaces, flow planning, airport design, the choice of retail categories – all of this has now reached quite high levels of optimization globally. Luxury is perhaps a good example, even though everyone has entered, it took some time to converge on the idea that travel retail is a unique channel in terms of exposure, visibility, and connection with a very appealing consumer profile. Another important genre that has been present for a long time and has gained considerable success in recent years is local products such as food and crafts, but also local products for wellness. We have also seen further acceleration in electronics, a category that has garnered a lot of interest from consumers/travelers due to convenience. Another category, which is an evergreen of travel retail, is that of spirits and fragrances. The particular trend, however, regarding consumer behavior, is an increasing focus on premium products from a quality perspective.

So, where are we heading?

As I mentioned, we are increasingly moving towards greater digitization of the shopping experience before, during, and after the journey, even in the travel retail channel. For me, this is a chapter where the sprint in the next 5 years will be enormous, both because affordable tools are now available and because consumers expect to have this kind of interaction. The other

aspect is the importance of the airport experience: therefore, investments by both brands and operators, to add to the act of purchase also the aspect of entertainment and, where possible, a convergence between food & beverage and retail. So, in summary, on one hand, a strong "humanization" with the evolution of the experience, and on the other, strong digitalization, which positions travel retail at the center of a hybrid and boundaryless interaction of space and time.

In essence, not so much a specific product but more of an experience.

Indeed, products are constantly evolving. If we look at airports with critical mass from a dimensional point of view, we find an enormous variety in terms of the range. There are certain products that are difficult to display in an airport context (if not for showcase reasons), but everything that is portable can become travel retail: there are even airports that have art galleries, spas, playgrounds. It is clear that this sector continues to evolve, as I mentioned, there is greater attention to adapting the design of terminals for real shopping experiences.

How would you like to conclude?

I am a deep optimist about the role of the channel because Covid-19 confirmed that traveling is one of the pillars of our sense of freedom: we were deprived of it due to the pandemic, and when we saw an initial opening, we took the opportunity to travel again, so much so that leisure travel has increased significantly compared to the past. We have become accustomed, in the context of the travel experience, to this fantastic convenience: exploring products, buying things that are useful, etc. And this desire to travel is in our genetic code.

Interview with Matteo Baù

Commercial Non-Aviation Director - Milan Bergamo Airport since 2006 From 2003 to 2006, he held the position of Purchasing Manager, also at Milan Bergamo Airport. In his airport management career, he has gained over 20 years of experience at "SEA Spa - Milan Malpensa and Linate Airports" and "SACBO Spa - Milan Orio al Serio Airport".

The travel retail sector has been severely affected by the Covid-19 pandemic; international travel restrictions have led to a drastic reduction in revenues for operators. In your opinion, what impact has the Covid-19 pandemic had on the choices of airport travel retail operators?

The pandemic has had a traumatic impact on the airport sector and everything related to it; this shock has generated a frightening revenue crisis, with operators having to resort to social safety nets in the most critical phase to try to save the entire industry. At Bergamo Airport, we tried to maintain continuity in decisions and interventions even in the early post-Covid-19 phase, so much so that we observed numbers similar to those before the pandemic in terms of passenger traffic. It should also be emphasized that some responses (mainly political, but also strategic) were late and inefficient, for example, some airports in Northern Europe saw their capacity reduced by 25%.

What are the main strategies adopted in this early post-Covid phase, and what will remain of these strategies?

Without a doubt, pervasive digitalization has been and still is one of the strategies that have been strengthened in this early post-Covid-19 phase, and it is a strategy that will consolidate in the near future. By digitalization, I mean a 360-degree approach, which has many areas of intervention; for example, even in the concept of parking, which for an airport like Milan-Bergamo has always been one of the main non-aviation core businesses, the airport has doubled its revenue in the last year through digitalization that began about 15 years ago. It should be noted that this surge during the post-Covid-19 period is not unstoppable; indeed, a slowdown is

already visible compared to the great results of the last year, heading towards a phase of "normalization."

From the perspective of consumer behavior, have you noticed any changes between pre and post-Covid? Do you think new emerging opportunities are opening up in the sector?

In our case, I can tell you that the changes in consumer behavior have been significant and, in part, unexpected. We had to cope not only with the pandemic and restrictions but also with inflation, which certainly did not give us a rosy revenue forecast; but towards the end of last year, we saw an incredible 50% increase in revenue compared to the previous period, which, upon thorough analysis, was due to a series of factors. Firstly, the emotional/psychological aspect: a desire to spend "regardless," due to the reopening of the sector after the restrictions. This factor alone would not have had such an effect if not parallelly associated with a series of activities to requalify the airport infrastructure and modernize the spaces in the terminals. Even here, such behavior is experiencing a physiological decline and is now "normalizing."

Digital transformation in airports is increasingly reducing activity times in the landside area (check-in, baggage, security checks, and passport control), preserving more dwell time in the commercial area; how do you think technology can further transform travel retail? And how can it assist in this regard?

This is a very broad topic: digital is a challenging approach in an infrastructure like an airport, where many operators with different but often integrated roles are present. This difficulty stems from both market and generational needs. Online check-in, for example, is a technology that reduces times and, at the same time, allows the storage of a series of passenger data which - net of privacy and the rest - would allow audience profiling and segmentation. But in some cases, through online check-in, it's the airline that tracks the passenger, while the paradox is that the airport operator might not even know that the passenger is passing through the terminal. However, there are some integrated check-in technologies, for example, that have been experimented with in Rome and Milan, allowing all the operators involved to benefit from them.

Most international airports have developed a greater focus on environmental sustainability, pursuing carbon neutrality goals. In your opinion, how are airport travel retail operators addressing sustainability and environmental and social impact? Are there any strategies to highlight?

The work we are doing in this historic phase at Milan-Bergamo airport certainly concerns the plastic-free policy in the retail sector, forcing commercial partners to reduce or even eliminate the use of plastic in packaging or products. Regarding the concept of "green," it should be said that, in some cases, it has become a sort of fashion internationally that needs to be followed more as a trend than with active policies: it is, however, a cultural and inevitable process that will have tangible results not before 10 years. In addition, my feeling is that it will be a real "added value" of the sector when the new generations (Millennials and Gen Z) become the main audience that will make reasoned choices even during purchases.

A final question about your personal vision of airport travel retail: in your opinion, what are the current trends? Are there certain categories gaining popularity compared to the past?

There are few differences from the pre-Covid phase in my opinion: quality food is perhaps the trend that remains most popular in travel retail, especially local products. I do not see any particular phenomenon as a trend in travel retail gaining ground, but the consideration to be made instead concerns the brands: fashion leads some specific brands to have a large market even in travel retail, but it is still a limited time because perhaps after 5 years, it is replaced by another brand.

Interview with Konstantinos Kouleris

More than 27 years of experience in the travel retail, retail and consulting sectors, heavily involved in the development of the non-aeronautical revenues and business growth of the:

- Hamad & Doha Intl. Airports in Qatar (Qatar Airways Group), commercial development and revenues improvement
- Athens Intl. Airport “Eleftherios Venizelos” in Greece, commercial development of all commercial zones of the new airport
- Larnaca Intl. Airport in Cyprus – consultation for the commercial development of the available lands and buildings in the airport’s premisses

Professional highlights:

- expert in the travel retail, non-aeronautical revenues, in the development of the Airports’ commercial zones (in the terminals) and available areas/facilities; (external areas/airport city)
- Experience in corporate governance – Member of the BOE and Deputy to the Chairman of the Board of the National Train Organization in Greece;
- International Advisor at the European Bank of Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Thank you in advance for your kind consideration and I remain at your disposal for any additional information/clarifications.

The travel retail has been severely affected by the Covid_19 pandemic; international travel restrictions have led to a drastic reduction of revenues for workers in the sector.

In your opinion, what impact has the covid_19 had on the choices of airport travel retail workers?

Due to this unforeseen situation, airport authorities and stakeholders working in the airport environment, took the decision to reduce their staff. The airlines put on hold most of their flights and staff, reduced their salaries by 40% at least, concessionaires reduced their personnel to the minimum required or put on hold all of them, if the store in the terminal was closed. Unfortunately a small number of employees didn't manage to get back their jobs post COVID as companies hired personnel with more advantageous terms and salaries for the companies.

Some airlines and stakeholders rehired their personnel, this is a good case of the COVID effect.

What are the main strategies adopted in this first post-covid period, and what will remain of these strategies?

After COVID airports try to come back to normalcy by securing all processes policies agreements and operations like pre COVID .

They operated again all the retail units, they tried to offer some relaxation in the agreements over the stakeholders that were heavily affected by the COVID, like extended for one or two years the contract duration, Lifting back old discounts offered previously to stakeholders, request again the monthly rentals and in general reestablish the commercial relationship with stakeholders to the previous status.

The concessions that were not profitable Pre COVID, we are not renewed and both parties (airport authorities and concessionaires) decided to end up their relationship.

Therefore, New opportunities for commercial senior cheese arrows with new contracts including close this we're predicting pandemic situations from now on.

And from a consumer behavior point of view, have you noticed any changes between pre and post-covid? Do you think new emerging opportunities are opening up in the travel retail in airport?

A passenger always wants to enjoy the airport experience, the flying experience to its full extent, therefore is expecting normal operations of an airport, regardless of if it is a COVID or a Non-COVID situation.

So, I would say that the behaviour remained the same. The only difference has been noticed to the safety measures implemented from the airports and how passengers appreciated these efforts. Indeed they were relaxed and feeling safe.

Emerging opportunities for the travel retail environment are basically related technological advancements, like contact contactless purchases, new product categories like sanitizers, contactless payments (i.e parking facilities) connect asking stop.

The concept of security in airport is always a very delicate question, especially in an historical period linked to uncertainty like this, from all points of view. How and how much can it affect the development of travel retail strategies in airport?

Security is very important aspect of airports operations for passengers, equipment and facilities safety. It should always be there regardless of pandemic cases or normal operations. It is very often that both parties, security and commercial department, are in conflict.

However, historically there is always a conflict between the safety & security and the commercial departments. In the airport the commercial departments are always trying to find additional space in order to develop more commercial activities. Security restrictions are always a burden for the commercial development and Security is always facing challenges from the commercial department.

The restrictions from the security are related to the width of the corridors for passengers circulation, the shape of the units, the areas that the commercial department wants to develop retail shops (i.e. close to screening points), etc. Even the advertising locations are an issue if the advertisement are creating confusion or offering misleading information.

In some cases it is very difficult or impossible to avoid or to ignore the safety rules and the restrictions and the commercial development cannot be realised.

However, if there is a common understanding and the primary target is passengers satisfaction, always a balance is found between safety rules and commercial development.

The digital transformation in airport is reducing more and more the timing of activities in the landside area (check-in, laggage, security check and passport control), saving more time for dwell time in the commercial area; in your opinion, how can technology transform travel retail again? And how can it help the travel retail?

Technology for sure can help minimise the required time for checking process, luggage drop off, immigration process, etc. For example in Hamad International Airport there is a self drop process for the languages, or faster screening equipment for passports and boarding cards.

Live maps in airports application are very helpful for passengers circulation offering Peace of Mind, relaxation and additional time for shopping.

Day by day, new technologies, improvement of existing , and innovative equipment are facilitating the whole boarding and arriving process, thus offering additional time to passengers for more shopping.

And which technological tools or solutions are most influencing the travel retail experience for travellers?

Regarding the boarding process all solutions or equipment that are facilitating the check in and the immigration process. The airports way finding applications are extremely helpful to the passengers. Geofence applications calculating the volume or the number of the passengers entering in specific areas or in the retail stores or in the gate lounges, are very helpful to collect data for further analysis, and improvement for airports and stores operations.

Many airports are creating e-commerce, online spaces to then pick-up the product directly at the airport. In your opinion, how important is to integrate online shopping with a physical place like the airport?

It is necessary now to integrate a physical place in the airport to collect pre-orders as e-commerce, day by day, is becoming a trend and it is estimated that in the course of the next five years e-commerce will increase by 30%.

Many people now are very familiar with the online shopping and collecting their purchases from physical stores. As many products are offered in highly discounted prices online, passengers are benefited from this offers, are very familiar of collecting their purchases from the airport they're visiting or departing from.

Most international airports have developed great attention to environmental sustainability, pursuing carbon neutrality aim. In your opinion, how are airport travel retail workers dealing with the issue of sustainability and environmental and social impact? Are there any strategies to highlight?

Well, airport travel retail workers through constant trainings are familiar in environmental issues, in the fact, as passengers are international travellers, very sensitive in environmental issues, travel retail workers must be aligned with environmental issues. Apart of that, airports in recent years

are very sensitive in environmental issues and therefore are contacting trainings to all airport staff.

Same applies to all sustainability issues and social impact. Through constant trainings and awareness developed by airports management, and in view of getting special awards like SKYTRAX awards, airport authorities are constantly investing on their stuff.

Last question about your personal vision of travel retail in airport: in your opinion, what are the current trends? Are there certain categories that are gaining popularity compared to the past?

Current trends in travel retail are related to the digitalization of the purchases, the easy buying process and the development of one-stop-shop, which is ideal for the travellers.

They would love to enter in one store and to the majority of their shopping, enjoying all the benefits of technology.

Wellness is a category that is not developed that much in airports but it's a rising trend. Passengers are seeking their personal relaxation, they love to indulge themselves and to offer some luxury.

Traditional shopping will remain as a need, as travellers love the physical touch and spending sometime in the retail shops. Luxury brands all always a high attraction for passengers and will always be.

Concluding traditional shopping with some touch of technology including e-commerce is the new trend.

Interview with Kevin Rozario

Journalist and editor, he has been covering the travel retail and wider aviation channels since the mid-1990s. He has written for all the main international B2B media in this sector and also cover travel retail at *Forbes.com*, and airport PPP projects for the advisory firm Modalis Infrastructure Partners (on their site AirportIR).

The travel retail has been severely affected by the Covid_19 pandemic; international travel restrictions have led to a drastic reduction of revenues for workers in the sector.

In your opinion, what impact has the covid_19 had on the choices of airport travel retail workers?

Travel retail was severely impacted by the pandemic. When it comes to the specific revenue impact for airport travel retail workers, much depended on the individual government subsidies and furlough schemes that were made available during the pandemic. This varied from country to country.

What are the main strategies adopted in this first post-covid period, and what will remain of these strategies?

In the post-Covid period airport retailers are recruiting store staff again at a rapid rate to ensure they can meet passenger demand that is higher than expected: so called 'revenge spending'. These companies are also spending more on store refits and animations to boost revenue/pax.

And from a consumer behavior point of view, have you noticed any changes between pre and post-covid? Do you think new emerging opportunities are opening up in the travel retail in airport?

In the initial post-pandemic phase passengers were spending more per head, probably because they were a travelling profile with more spending power. As travel normalises the spending patterns will probably also moderate.

The concept of security in airport is always a very delicate question, especially in an historical period linked to uncertainty like this, from all points of view.

How and how much can it affect the development of travel retail strategies in airport?

Security can influence retail spending. Long queues can reduce time spent in the shops, and also negatively impact a passenger's mood and thus their likelihood to shop. Airports usually allow a physical space between the security area and the walk-through duty-free shops so that passengers can decompress and organise themselves before going into the stores.

The digital transformation in airport is reducing more and more the timing of activities in the landside area (check-in, luggage, security check and passport control), saving more time for dwell time in the commercial area; in your opinion, how can technology transform travel retail again? And how can it help the travel retail?

Technology is allowing retailers to track passengers from home to departure gate and message them at the right points on their journey to remind them of special offers in a store nearby for example. Passengers can also click-and-collect products, which ensures a sale for retailers before a traveller even enters the airport. Tech via loyalty cards also means easy access to passenger data (eg spending habits) which can be used to alter the shopping offer in the airport or target specific offers to each passenger (just like supermarkets already do in domestic retailing).

And which technological tools or solutions are most influencing the travel retail experience for travellers?

Click-and-collect is the most common as it is the easiest to set up. Brands have been testing digital promotions using social media 'opportunities' as a pull for younger Gen Zs.

Many airports are creating e-commerce, online spaces to then pick-up the product directly at the airport.

In your opinion, how important is to integrate online shopping with a physical place like the airport?

Creating the 'phygital' offer is important. Online shopping was seen as essential during the pandemic, but it has tapered off a bit now as consumers like to enter physical environments.

However, it remains vital that retailers can show they are savvy in the digital arena... it adds incremental revenue at the very least.

Most international airports have developed great attention to environmental sustainability, pursuing carbon neutrality aim.

In your opinion, how are airport travel retail workers dealing with the issue of sustainability and environmental and social impact? Are there any strategies to highlight?

Most travel retailers are taking a sustainability position, How worthy these positions are remains debateable. Lagardere Travel Retail and Heinemann probably lead the sector in this regard. Largely on store fittings and selection of brands that fit their sustainability criteria.

Last question about your personal vision of travel retail in airport: in your opinion, what are the current trends? Are there certain categories that are gaining popularity compared to the past?

Right now, luxury goods are doing exceptionally well. This seems to be a post-pandemic reaction and may fade a little. However, with the Chinese now travelling again, luxury will remain a staple of travel retail. Personally I think the airport concession model needs to change in order to democratise travel retail to allow more mainstream and newcomer brands into airports. That way, more passengers can shop, and the retail environment can become more diverse and interesting. This variety and choice has been lacking in travel retail.